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R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)
 DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs
 DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.

² **Dissemination level:** Use one of the following codes (in consistence with the Description of the Action)

PU: Public, fully open, e.g. web
 SEN: Sensitive, limited under conditions of the Grant Agreement

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List of Abbreviations and Definitions

The abbreviations and definitions used in the deliverable are based on the AIDAVA Glossary³.

Key definitions for this document:

Terms	Description
Personal Health Knowledge Graph (PHKG)	Format for storing curated personal health data: all data sources from a patient are transformed, curated/cleaned and integrated into a single knowledge graph including the curated data from one individual
Health Data Intermediary (HDI)	Organisation allowing citizens to access, manage their personal health data and control how it is shared. In AIDAVA, they are managing non-hospital data (e.g. medical device app, patient reported outcomes, GP data).
AIDAVA prototype	Software application being developed as part of the AIDAVA project, to support ingestion, curation and publishing of personal health data.
Requirements = functional + non-functional requirements	Requirements are clear, concise, and specific statements that describe what a software system should do or the qualities it must possess. Requirements can be differentiated into functional requirements and non-functional requirements
Functional requirements (FR)	Specific features or capabilities that a system or application must have in order to meet the needs of its users: what the AIDAVA health data curation and publishing virtual assistant does . These requirements describe the AIDAVA health data curation and publishing virtual assistant's behaviour, or what it must do.
Non-functional requirements (NFR)	Describe the qualities that a system or application must possess in order to be considered usable or effective. These requirements do not describe what the AIDAVA health data curation and publishing virtual assistant does, but rather how it does it .
Epics	Agile term. Group of requirements that represents a significant and complex piece of work. Epics are used to capture and describe requirements or features that are too big to be completed in a single development iteration (sprint) and require further decomposition into smaller, manageable user stories.
Product	A software product is the final, fully-developed version of a software application that is intended for release and use by end-users. (source: ChatGPT)
SIP	Study Information Package – the information material patients receive when they are considering to participate in the AIDAVA prototype assessment study
ICF	Informed Consent Form – patients must sign this if they want to participate in the AIDAVA prototype assessment study
DPIA	Data Processing Impact Assessment – a tool to assess and mitigate the risks of data processing to individuals' rights and freedoms

³ <https://www.aidava.eu/helpdesk/glossary>

Executive Summary

This document describes the activities undertaken in Phase 2 of Task 1.3 of the AIDAVA project. It provides an update of Deliverable D1.3 based on the evaluation of achievement (or not) of the requirements, which were defined in Phase 1 of Task 1.3 for the AIDAVA prototype, as well as an updated list of business requirements and related acceptance criteria elaborated for Generation 2 of the AIDAVA prototype (AIDAVA G2).

To achieve this, activities in Phase 2 of Task 1.3 included the following steps:

1. Evaluation of requirements met in AIDAVA G1.
The acceptance criteria fulfilment assessment revealed that 85% of the 'blocking', 52% of the 'major' and 38% of the 'minor' acceptance criteria, which were elaborated in Phase 1 of Task 1.3 and deemed relevant for an AIDAVA prototype, were already fulfilled by the Generation 1 of the AIDAVA prototype (AIDAVA G1).
2. New requirements and related acceptance criteria derived on the experiences and findings from the AIDAVA G1 prototype assessment study (see *Deliverable D1.7. Report on G1 performance*).
3. New requirements and related acceptance criteria were formulated based on the results of analysis of legal provisions in WP4 (see *Deliverable 4.8. Regulatory Conformance Analysis of AI Development Pipeline*).
4. A consolidated list of requirements and acceptance criteria was compiled based on the results of the previous steps: starting from those acceptance criteria which were defined in the first phase of Task 1.3 for an AIDAVA prototype and not yet fulfilled by AIDAVA G1, new requirements and acceptance criteria, which evolved from practical experience with AIDAVA G1 development and testing as well as from explainability needs, were added.
5. All acceptance criteria in the consolidated list were assigned a level of severity (blocking, major, minor) from users' point of view so that the resulting list of business requirements and acceptance criteria can give guidance for the development of the AIDAVA G2 prototype.

The updated consolidated business requirements list for the AIDAVA G2 prototype comprises 198 requirements (110 defined for G1 and not fulfilled, 88 new as a result of the G1 evaluation) and 355 related acceptance criteria (34 blocking, 209 major, 112 minor). 47% of the acceptance criteria were formulated from the patients' perspective. This is in line with AIDAVA seeing patients as the main user group for the 'AI-powered virtual assistant for health data curation and publishing'.

This updated list of business requirements and related acceptance criteria will be further used as the basis for development of the AIDAVA G2 prototype. GND will integrate these business requirements with the technical requirements identified through the AIDAVA G1 development and testing, discuss with all AIDAVA development partners, and prioritise from the developers' point of view. This process will lead to an improved AIDAVA G2 prototype as per the specified requirements.

1 Introduction

Business requirements describe from the point of view of a system's stakeholders (i.e. users, consumers, customers) *what* functionalities the system shall provide, and *why* these functionalities are needed.

For the 'AI-powered data curation and publishing virtual assistant' (AIDAVA) five user groups were identified:

- *Patients* - They are the main user group. In their role as curator, the patient ingests their personal data from the different source systems, initiates the curation process and answers questions from the AIDAVA health data curation and publishing virtual assistant whenever needed. In their role as data consumer, the patient requests to forward their personal data to the local Health Data Intermediary (HDI) for further visualisation.
- *Expert Curators* - Support patients in curating their data; patients may delegate the curation tasks to expert curators whenever the system's requests for human curation help require a level of health literacy or digital literacy that the patient does not have.
- *Data Users* - Access a data extract published from AIDAVA (with patient consent) to answer a specific need in clinical care or in clinical research.
- *Administrators* - Responsible for configuring, integrating, and testing the AIDAVA solution (e.g. at a hospital site)
- *3rd party app developers* - Develop applications which utilise AIDAVA's APIs (application programming interfaces)⁴ either to provide health data to AIDAVA or to extract and reuse curated health data from AIDAVA.

In the first phase of Task 1.3, business requirements for each of these user groups were gathered, concrete acceptance criteria were formulated, and each of these acceptance criteria was provided with a level of severity (blocking, major, minor, out of scope) indicating the importance of having that acceptance criterium fulfilled in the AIDAVA prototype. Furthermore, for each of the requirements the team identified also the need to have it fulfilled in the prototype or only in a future project. This process of requirements elicitation as well as the resulting comprehensive list of business requirements has been described in detail in the Deliverable D1.3.

The aim of the second phase of Task 1.3 was to elaborate a list of business requirements and related acceptance criteria for the AIDAVA G2 prototype by updating the list of business requirements elicited during the first phase of Task 1.3 and the related acceptance criteria based on the experiences and findings gained during the development phase of the AIDAVA G1 prototype and through the AIDAVA G1 prototype assessment study.

This Deliverable D1.9 is the result of the work conducted during Phase 2 of Task 1.3 in Work Package 1 of the AIDAVA project. This document is structured as follows: Section 2 gives a detailed overview of the activities conducted in Phase 2 of Task 1.3. Section 3 describes the results of the acceptance evaluation of the AIDAVA G1 prototype and lists the consolidated business requirements and related acceptance criteria for AIDAVA G2. Section 4 gives a concise summary and Section 5 outlines how the defined business requirements and acceptance criteria will further be used in the AIDAVA project.

⁴ In the context of the prototype to be delivered during the AIDAVA project, all integration will be done through existing and/or prototype APIs and/or through asynchronous data transfer based on predefined data transfer specification to minimise disruption with productive systems.

2 Description of Activities

To achieve the goal of the second phase of Task 1.3, the following main activities were conducted:

1. The list of requirements and acceptance criteria elaborated during the first phase of Task 1.3 was re-visited to check which of these acceptance criteria were already fulfilled by the AIDAVA G1 prototype.
 - Acceptance criteria fulfilment assessment for AIDAVA G1 prototype
 - Acceptance evaluation of AIDAVA G1 prototype
2. New requirements and related acceptance criteria were formulated based on the experiences and findings from the AIDAVA G1 prototype assessment study.
3. New requirements and related acceptance criteria were formulated based on the results of analysis of legal provisions in WP4 of AIDAVA.
4. A consolidated list of requirements and acceptance criteria was compiled based on the results of the previous steps.
5. All acceptance criteria in the consolidated list were assigned a level of severity from users' point of view so that the resulting list of business requirements and acceptance criteria can give guidance for the development of the AIDAVA G2 prototype.

In the following subsections, these activities are described in detail.

2.1 Reviewing Business Requirements Elaborated in Phase 1 of Task 1.3

In Phase 1 of Task 1.3 a comprehensive list of 487 business requirements with a total of 679 related acceptance criteria was developed. From this comprehensive list, 265 business requirements with a total of 464 related acceptance criteria were deemed to be relevant for an AIDAVA prototype.

2.1.1 Acceptance Criteria Fulfilment Assessment for AIDAVA G1 Prototype

The first task in Phase 2 of Task 1.3 was to review this list of 464 acceptance criteria in order to assess for each of these acceptance criteria whether or not this acceptance criterium was already fulfilled by the AIDAVA G1 prototype.

To facilitate this task, the list of requirements and related acceptance criteria, which were elaborated in Phase 1 of Task 1.3 and deemed to be relevant for the AIDAVA prototype, was copied into a shared spreadsheet in the AIDAVA Google Drive. In the following, this list of requirements including the related acceptance criteria is called "prototype-related Phase 1 requirements".

The first assessment round for the functional requirements was done by MUG, NEMC, UM, GND and MIDATA, as these partners had got first-hand experience with the AIDAVA G1 prototype either from users' point of view in the test sites (MUG, NEMC and UM) or from developers' point of view (GND and MIDATA). These five partners went through the list of "prototype-related Phase 1 requirements" individually and stated in the respective column of the shared spreadsheet for each of the acceptance criteria of a functional requirement their opinion regarding whether or not that acceptance criterium was fulfilled by the AIDAVA G1 prototype from their point of view. Thereby, MUG, NEMC and UM assessed the AIDAVA G1 prototype from users' point of view as they had experienced the AIDAVA G1 prototype from patients', expert curators' and data users' (clinicians) perspective through their involvement with testing the AIDAVA G1 prototype in the clinical sites. GND and MIDATA assessed the AIDAVA G1 prototype from developers' and 3rd party app developers'/HDI's perspective respectively.

The shared spreadsheet also provided a dedicated column for comments, which the partners used for example to explain their point of view, describe any unclear aspects, or provide additional information.

MODIFIED Acceptance Criterion	Acceptance Criterion fulfilled by G1? (consolidated)	Acceptance Criterion fulfilled by G1? MUG opinion	Acceptance Criterion fulfilled by G1? NEMC opinion	Acceptance Criterion fulfilled by G1? UM opinion	Acceptance Criterion fulfilled by G1? MIDATA opinion empty = don't know	Acceptance Criterion fulfilled by G1? GND opinion	Comments (discussion of requirements for G2)
The system takes into account the information of the user profile of the user (health literacy, digital literacy, related curator) when asking help to the user through a HITL dialogue in the curation process	no	no	no	no		no	this is planned for G2

Figure 1: In a shared spreadsheet WP1 partners assessed whether or not the acceptance criteria defined in phase 1 of Task 1.3 were fulfilled by the AIDAVA G1 prototype

In the next step, a consolidated view among all T1.3 partners regarding the fulfilment of functional acceptance criteria by the AIDAVA G1 prototype had to be achieved. For those acceptance criteria where the individual assessments in the shared spreadsheet were congruent, the respective assessment was implicitly agreed as a consolidated view. To achieve a consolidated view for the remaining acceptance criteria, weekly online meetings with the whole T1.3 team (MUG, NEMC, UM, GND, MIDATA, b!lo, EHN, DFP) were organised. In these meetings, the T1.3 team discussed each of these acceptance criteria where the individual assessments were not congruent or where comments indicated need for clarification. Through this process a consolidated assessment of whether or not the respective functional acceptance criterium was fulfilled by the AIDAVA G1 prototype was reached.

For the non-functional requirements in the “prototype-related Phase 1 requirements” list, the assessment of whether or not the related non-functional acceptance criteria were fulfilled by the AIDAVA G1 prototype was done in separate dedicated online meetings by b!lo, GND, MIDATA and UM.

During the assessment procedures, only those acceptance criteria which were assessed by the team as completely fulfilled by the AIDAVA G1 prototype were marked as “yes” in the shared spreadsheet. All acceptance criteria, which were only partly fulfilled or where the team was not sure that the respective acceptance criterium was completely fulfilled by the AIDAVA G1 prototype, were marked as “no” in the shared spreadsheet.

2.1.2 Acceptance Evaluation of the AIDAVA G1 Prototype

As described in Deliverable D1.3, acceptance evaluation of the AIDAVA G1 prototype shall be based on the results of the ‘acceptance criteria fulfilment assessment for AIDAVA G1 prototype’ (as described in Subsection 2.1.1 of this document) where each acceptance criterium was assessed as “fulfilled by AIDAVA G1 prototype” or “not fulfilled by AIDAVA G1 prototype”, and on the values listed in Table 1:

- **Weight:** in Table 1 a weight-value is assigned to each requirement category, indicating the importance of that specific requirement category for the prototype⁵
- **%_fulfilled:** the percentage of fulfilled acceptance criteria (*%_fulfilled*) is calculated in each requirement category for 'blocking', 'major' and 'minor' acceptance criteria separately as depicted in the following example for 'major' acceptance criteria in the requirement category “data ingestion” - here written as *AC_(data ingestion, major)*:

⁵ It is expected that the weight will need to be adapted for the product

$$\%_{\text{fulfilled}}(\text{data ingestion, major}) = \frac{\text{number of fulfilled AC}(\text{data ingestion, major})}{\text{number of all AC}(\text{data ingestion, major})}$$

- **TOTAL %_fulfilled:** is calculated separately for 'blocking', 'major' and 'minor' acceptance criteria as the sum of the weighted %_fulfilled (i.e. [Weight * % fulfilled]) over all requirement categories
- **Minimum required (%_fulfilled):** the “Minimum required (%_fulfilled)” values given in Table 1 for 'blocking', 'major' and 'minor' acceptance criteria in each category, as well as the minimum TOTAL-value across all categories mark the threshold that should be reached by the values calculated based on the results of the ‘acceptance criteria fulfilment assessment’ for the AIDAVA prototype.

Table 1: Acceptance evaluation metrics for functional and non-functional requirements as defined in Deliverable D1.3

Functional Requirement Categories	Weight	Minimum required (%_fulfilled)		
		Blocking	Major	Minor
Data Ingestion	10%	100%	80%	As much as possible
Data Curation	15%		90%	
User Interaction	15%		80%	
Data Publishing	10%			
User Management	15%			
Data Use	10%			
Quality Management	15%			
Integration	10%			
TOTAL - formula	Sum all Weights	Sum all (Weight * %_fulfilled)		
TOTAL - value	100%	100%	80%	NA

Non-functional Requirement Categories	Weight	Minimum required (%_fulfilled)		
		Blocking	Major	Minor
Performance	5%	100%	80%	As much as possible
Scalability	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	
Availability	5%	80%	80%	
Reliability	10%	100%	80%	
Maintainability	5%	80%	80%	
Serviceability	15%	80%	80%	
Security & Data privacy	15%	100%	80%	
Regulatory	10%	100%	80%	
Usability	15%	100%	80%	
Automation	15%	100%	80%	
General Principles	5%	80%	80%	
TOTAL - formula	Sum all Weights	Sum all (Weight * %_fulfilled)		
TOTAL - value	100%	90%	80%	NA

2.2 Capturing New Business Requirements

2.2.1 Formulating Requirements Evolving from AIDAVA G1 Development and Testing

A shared document titled “potential-new-requirements-for-G2” was set up in the AIDAVA Google Drive to facilitate collection of new requirements, which were coming up after Phase 1 of Task 1.3. Partners were encouraged to write into that shared document any requirements which evolved from practical experience with AIDAVA G1 prototype development and testing as well as from discussion of acceptance criteria among the WP1 partners in the course of re-visiting the business requirements as described in the previous Subsection 2.1. In addition, the Deliverable *D1.7 Report on G1 performance* and the shared document where the findings from the AIDAVA G1 prototype assessment study in the test sites had been collected were carefully analysed to identify all hints towards new requirements for AIDAVA. Furthermore, as this shall be an important part of AIDAVA G2 according to the Grant Agreement, a specific focus was also put on identifying requirements with regards to explainability which evolved both from the experience gained during the AIDAVA G1 testing as well as from analysis of the deliverable D5.2 “Analysis on explainability for different skill levels; delivery of explainability module for G2”.

All notes collected in the “potential-new-requirements-for-G2” document and all relevant aspects identified in the documents describing the findings from the AIDAVA G1 prototype assessment study were properly formulated as requirements in the following form:

As a [user role], [doing step of the user journey], I want [needed functionality], so that [reason/expected benefit by the user].

Thereby, it was made sure that each requirement has a need and is clear so that it cannot be misunderstood.

2.2.2 Elaborating Requirements for Compliance with the EU AI Act

With the EU AI Act entering into force on 1st of August 2024, new requirements for legal compliance came up for AI-based systems such as the ‘AI-powered data curation and publishing virtual assistant’ (AIDAVA). According to the EU AI Act, a future ‘AI-powered data curation and publishing virtual assistant’ would be a high-risk application as it is processing personal health data, and thus it would need to comply with the respective legal provisions of the AI Act.

In WP4 legal provisions, which might be relevant for AIDAVA, have been analysed and recommendations for regulatory conformance are described in Deliverable D4.8 Regulatory Conformance Analysis of AI Development. The comprehensive table of recommendations formulated in Section 3.6 of Deliverable D4.8 was used as a starting point. In close collaboration with WP4, concrete acceptance criteria were formulated for the requirements. These acceptance criteria and their prioritisation as 'blocking', 'major' or 'minor' was discussed and agreed with the T1.3 team in a dedicated online session.

Since the EU AI Act will only be effective from 2nd of August 2026, which is after the development and testing of the AIDAVA G2 prototype, all these requirements are deemed to be out of scope for the prototype but clearly in scope of a future product.

2.3 Elaboration of a Consolidated Requirements List for AIDAVA G2

We created a combined list of

1. those prototype-related business requirements and acceptance criteria, which had been elaborated in Phase 1 of Task 1.3 and were assessed as not yet completely fulfilled by the AIDAVA G1 prototype (as described in Subsection 2.1 of this document), and
2. the new requirements, which evolved from AIDAVA G1 assessment (as described in Subsection 2.2 of this document).

This list was copied into a shared spreadsheet and formed the starting point for elaboration of a consolidated list of business requirements for the AIDAVA G2 prototype.

As a first step, all new requirements were assigned a suitable epic category from the list of epics, which had been defined during the first phase of Task 1.3: ingestion, curation, user interaction, publishing, user management, data use, quality management, integration, training/documentation and non-functional requirement. Then, similar requirements were grouped and, if feasible, merged.

In a next step, for each of the new requirements acceptance criteria were formulated and added in the spreadsheet. Acceptance criteria are the criteria used to evaluate whether the prototype and later the product fulfil the requirements from the different user groups. To ensure that the formulated acceptance criteria will be suitable for that purpose, for the phrasing of acceptance criteria clear rules were followed:

1. Every acceptance criterion by itself needs to be very specific and measurable. It must be evident if a criterion is reached or not. If needed, useful measures shall be added (e.g. once a day, minimum 90% of xxx, or similar).
2. One row of acceptance criteria cannot hold more than one criterion – if the word “and” or commas or second sentences appear in an acceptance criterion, this can indicate the need to split the criterion into several criteria.
3. All of the acceptance criteria of one requirement together should cover every aspect of the respective requirement including the rationale.

Finally, all acceptance criteria were re-visited and checked against these rules. Some acceptance criteria were found to be phrased ambiguous and needed to be re-formulated to make them clearer, some needed to be split as they included more than one criterion, and some needed to be duplicated as they were formulated for more than one user group.

2.4 Prioritisation of the Acceptance Criteria

In a final step, all acceptance criteria included in the consolidated business requirements list were “prioritised”. This means, each of the acceptance criteria was assigned to one of the following categories according to its importance for the AIDAVA G2 prototype from users’ point of view:

- in scope of the G2 prototype with the following level of severity in terms of acceptance
 - blocking: critical, if not present the AIDAVA health data curation and publishing virtual assistant prototype is not acceptable
 - major: should be present
 - minor: would be nice to have
- out of scope of the G2 prototype (but would be in scope of an “AIDAVA-based” product)

This task was done in parallel by small teams of partners, whereby each team was responsible for prioritising the acceptance criteria of a specific user group or a certain category, as shown in the following table:

Team	Prioritising acceptance criteria
EHN, DFP, MUG, NEMC	user group: patients
MUG, NEMC	user group: expert curators
NEMC, UM, b!lo	user group: data users (clinicians)
MIDATA	user group: 3 rd party app developers
b!lo, GND, UM	user group: administrators & site administrators
IHD	category: regulatory requirements

After the teams had finalised their prioritisation tasks, all acceptance criteria to which a need for further clarification or input from other partners had evolved during this prioritisation task, were discussed among all T1.3 partners in weekly online meetings. In addition, all acceptance criteria which had been prioritised as 'blocking' by the responsible teams were re-visited during these weekly online meetings with all T1.3 partners. In these meetings, the responsible team explained their decision to assign 'blocking' to specific acceptance criteria in order to ensure that all partners understand why those acceptance criteria are so critical from users' point of view.

3 Results

3.1 Acceptance Criteria Fulfilment of the AIDAVA G1 Prototype

In Phase 1 of Task 1.3, 265 business requirements with a total of 462 related acceptance criteria were deemed to be relevant for an AIDAVA prototype. As shown in Table 2, these 462 acceptance criteria comprised 325 functional acceptance criteria, 68 acceptance criteria related to training & documentation, and 69 non-functional acceptance criteria. Of these 462 acceptance criteria, 72 were prioritised as 'blocking', 310 as 'major' and 80 as 'minor' with respect to acceptability of the prototype from users' point of view in phase 1 of Task 1.3.

Table 2 shows also, the distribution of the functional acceptance criteria over the epics (onboarding, ingestion, curation, user interaction, publishing, user management, data use, quality management, integration) as well as the distribution of the non-functional acceptance criteria over the categories (serviceability/helpdesk, availability, general principles/design, regulatory, reliability, maintainability, performance/automation, security & data privacy, usability & support), as defined in Phase 1 of Task 1.3.

These 462 acceptance criteria were re-visited in Phase 2 of Task 1.3 and assessed whether or not they have been fulfilled by the first generation of the AIDAVA prototype. Table 2 gives an overview of the results of this assessment including the number and % of acceptance criteria, which have been assessed to be fulfilled by AIDAVA G1. Of the 462 prototype-related acceptance criteria defined in Phase 1 of Task 1.3, 253 were assessed to be already fulfilled by AIDAVA G1. As shown in Table 2, these 253 acceptance criteria comprise 196 functional acceptance criteria, 4 acceptance criteria related to training & documentation, and 53 non-functional acceptance criteria. In total, 61 (85%) of the 72 'blocking' acceptance criteria, 162 (52%) of the 310 'major' acceptance criteria, and 30 (38%) of the 80 'minor' acceptance criteria have been fulfilled by the AIDAVA G1 prototype. This corresponds to the development strategy where the team focused on blocking requirements before major ones and certainly before minor ones.

Table 2 shows also the distribution of the already fulfilled functional acceptance criteria over the epics (data ingestion (incl. onboarding), data curation, user interaction, data publishing, user management, data use, quality management, integration) as well as the distribution of the already fulfilled non-functional acceptance criteria over the categories (serviceability/helpdesk, availability, general principles/design, maintainability, performance/automation, regulatory, reliability, security & data privacy, usability & support).

Table 2: Number of acceptance criteria defined in Phase 1 of T1.3, which were assessed to be already fulfilled by the AIDAVA G1 prototype

Acceptance criteria categories	Number of acceptance criteria relevant for the AIDAVA G1 prototype											
	total			blocking			major			minor		
	defined	fulfilled by G1		defined	fulfilled by G1		defined	fulfilled by G1		defined	fulfilled by G1	
Functional	325	196	60%	49	40	82%	220	134	60%	56	22	39%
Data Ingestion (Onboarding)	56	45	80%	6	6	100%	44	35	80%	6	4	67%
Data Curation	78	50	64%	7	7	100%	62	38	61%	9	5	56%
User Interaction	22	16	73%	7	6	86%	13	10	77%	2	0	0%
Data Publishing	52	30	58%	12	6	50% ⁶	33	20	61%	7	4	57%
User Management	43	24	56%	1	0	-	22	17	77%	20	7	35%
Data Use	33	11	33%	5	4	80%	25	7	28%	3	0	-
Quality Management	21	0	0%	0	0	-	14	0	0%	7	0	-
Integration	20	20	100%	11	11	100%	7	7	100%	2	2	100%
Training & Documentation	68	4	6%	1	1	100%	52	1	2%	15	2	13%
Non-functional	69	53	77%	22	20	91%	38	27	71%	9	6	67%
Serviceability/Helpdesk	15	11	73%	2	2	100%	11	7	64%	2	2	100%
Availability	3	3	100%	0	0	-	2	2	100%	1	1	100%
General Principles/Design	8	8	100%	2	2	100%	5	5	100%	1	1	100%
Maintainability	6	3	50%	1	1	100%	5	2	40%	0	0	-
Performance/Automation	7	7	100%	2	2	100%	4	4	100%	1	1	100%
Regulatory	6	5	83%	4	4	100%	1	1	100%	1	0	-
Reliability	4	4	100%	1	1	100%	2	2	100%	1	1	100%
Security & Data Privacy	13	13	100%	10	10	100%	3	3	100%	0	0	-
Usability & Support	7	1	14%	0	0	-	5	1	20%	2	0	-
All acceptance criteria	462	252	55%	72	61	85%	310	162	52%	80	30	38%

⁶ The main reason for such a low score is related to the lack of completeness of the PHKG in G1, itself resulting from failure of suboptimal tools used in G1 as discussed in D1.7. Report on G1 Performance.

3.2 Acceptance Evaluation of the AIDAVA G1 Prototype

As described in Subsection 2.1.2 of this document acceptance evaluation of the AIDAVA G1 prototype shall be based on the results of the 'acceptance criteria fulfilment assessment for AIDAVA G1 prototype' for the 'blocking' and 'major' functional and non-functional acceptance criteria (as displayed in Table 2), and on the acceptance evaluation metrics values listed in Table 1 of this document.

In the first evaluation step, for each of the categories of functional acceptance criteria and non-functional acceptance criteria the share of 'blocking' acceptance criteria fulfilled by the AIDAVA G1 prototype (% value listed in Table 2) and the share of 'major' acceptance criteria fulfilled by the AIDAVA G1 prototype (% value listed in Table 2) is compared with the respective minimum required %values listed in Table 1.

Table 3 and Table 4 show the results of this evaluation step for functional acceptance criteria categories and non-functional acceptance criteria categories respectively. In these tables the minimum required values (taken from Table 1) are listed in blue font. The %_fulfilled values for blocking and major acceptance criteria (taken from Table 2) are compared to the respective minimum required values. To make the evaluation result visible at a glance, in Table 3 and Table 4 all %_fulfilled values, which pass the evaluation criterion, are highlighted with light-green background.

As can be seen from Table 3 and Table 4, the AIDAVA G1 prototype passes the acceptance evaluation for the majority of non-functional acceptance criteria categories. A strong majority (82%) of the blocking functional requirements, as agreed with the business team, was met by AIDAVA G1. Major requirements were met to an acceptable level (60%), and minor requirements were partially met (39%) - reflecting the strategy to prioritise blocking requirements in the development.

Table 3: Acceptance Evaluation of the AIDAVA G1 prototype for functional acceptance criteria categories

Functional acceptance criteria	blocking			major				
	defined	fulfilled	required	defined	fulfilled	required		
Data Ingestion	6	6 (100%)	82%	100%	44	35 (80%)	80%	
Data Curation	7	7 (100%)			62	38 (61%)	64%	90%
User Interaction	7	6 (86%)			13	10 (77%)		
Data Publishing	12	6 (50%)			33	20 (61%)	50%	80%
User Management	1	0 (0%)			22	17 (77%)		
Data Use	5	4 (80%)			25	7 (28%)		
Quality Management	-	-			14	0 (0%)		
Integration	11	11 (100%)			7	7 (100%)		

Table 4: Acceptance Evaluation of the AIDAVA G1 prototype for non-functional acceptance criteria categories

Non-functional acceptance criteria	blocking			major				
	defined	fulfilled	required	defined	fulfilled	required		
Serviceability/Helpdesk	2	2	100%	80%	11	7	64%	80%
Availability	-	-	-	80%	2	2	100%	80%
General Principles/Design	2	2	100%	80%	5	5	100%	80%
Maintainability	1	1	100%	80%	5	2	40%	80%
Performance/Automation	2	2	100%	100%	4	4	100%	80%
Regulatory	4	4	100%	100%	1	1	100%	80%
Reliability	1	1	100%	100%	2	2	100%	80%
Security & Data Privacy	10	10	100%	100%	3	3	100%	80%
Usability & Support	-	-	-	100%	5	1	20%	80%

3.3 Business Requirements for the AIDAVA G2 Prototype

The consolidated list of business requirements elaborated for the AIDAVA G2 prototype in Phase 2 of Task 1.3 comprises 198 requirements, whereby **110** of these requirements have been **defined already in Phase 1** of Task 1.3 but were not yet completely fulfilled by the AIDAVA G1 prototype, and **88** new requirements were **added in Phase 2** of Task 1.3 derived from practical experience with AIDAVA G1 prototype development and testing and including also the requirements for explainability.

For these 198 requirements, which are deemed to be in scope of the AIDAVA prototype, in total 355 acceptance criteria were formulated, whereby 168 of these acceptance criteria are related to the new requirements which have been added in Phase 2 of Task 1.3. In total, 34 acceptance criteria are prioritised from users' point of view as 'blocking', 209 as 'major' and 112 as 'minor' (see Table 5).

Table 5 gives an overview of the number of acceptance criteria defined for the AIDAVA G2 prototype from the point of view of the different AIDAVA user groups. As can be seen, the vast majority of acceptance criteria was formulated from patients' perspective. This is in line with the fact that patients are seen as the main user group for the 'AI-powered virtual assistant for health data curation'.

Table 5: Number of acceptance criteria defined for the AIDAVA G2 prototype from point of view of the different user groups

User group	Number of acceptance criteria relevant for the AIDAVA G2 prototype			
	total	blocking	major	minor
3rd party app developers	17	5	4	8
administrators / site administrators	26	0	13	13
data users / clinicians	72	3	44	25
expert curators	71	5	43	23
patients	169	21	105	43
all user groups	355	34	209	112

Table 6 gives an overview of the distribution of the defined acceptance criteria among functional requirements (split into different categories), non-functional requirements and requirements related to training & documentation.

Table 6: Number of prototype-related acceptance criteria defined in the different categories

Categories	Number of acceptance criteria relevant for the AIDAVA G2 prototype			
	total	blocking	major	minor
Functional	289	32	166	91
Data Ingestion (incl. Onboarding)	22	0	6	16
Data Curation	49	10	22	17
User Interaction	85	8	53	24
Data Publishing	46	9	30	7
User Management	20	1	4	15
Data Use	30	3	24	3
Quality Management	36	1	26	9
Integration	1	0	1	0
Training & Documentation	49	2	30	17
Non-functional	17	0	13	4

In the following subsections, the functional requirements, non-functional requirements as well as the requirements related to training & documentation are further detailed.

Note: Some of the business requirements are shared requirements from several user groups, as these requirements were formulated from the point of view of more than one user group. The related acceptance criteria, however, are always phrased for a single user group so that it was possible to prioritise each acceptance criterium from the perspective of the respective user group. Therefore, sometimes several identical acceptance criteria from the perspective of different user groups are related to a shared requirement. These identical acceptance criteria have got the same acceptance criterion ID followed by an indication of the related user group, whereby -p stands for patients, -c for expert curators, and -u stands for data users. For example, AC0057.1-u is an acceptance criterion from the point of view of data users, and AC0057.1-c is (the identical) acceptance criterion from the point of view of expert curators.

3.3.1 Functional Requirements

This section describes the functional requirements elaborated for the AIDAVA G2 prototype. In the following paragraphs, these functional requirements and related acceptance criteria are grouped into categories following the epics identified in Deliverable D2.3 - Solution Design:

- Data Ingestion
- Data Curation
- User Interaction
- Data Publishing
- User Management
- Data Use
- Quality Management

Each acceptance criterion is assigned a severity level from the perspective of the respective user groups.

Data Ingestion

13 functional requirements concerning data ingestion to AIDAVA have been assessed in phase 2 of Task 1.3 to be relevant for the AIDAVA prototype. For these 13 functional requirements in total 22 acceptance criteria have been defined.

Requirement ID	Requirement	Severity (for G2)	Acceptance Criterion ID	Acceptance Criterion
C0011	As a patient ingesting data, I want all data to be automatically ingested into the AIDAVA health data curation and publishing virtual assistant without my input so that I can only focus on curating	minor	AC0011.4	The user can filter the list of data sources that can be ingested by data source type, period of content, source organisation (hospital versus HDI).
		minor	AC0011.5	The user can specify which data shall be ingested automatically by data source type, period of content, source organisation (hospital versus HDI).
C1124	As a patient using AIDAVA, I want that any documents which were uploaded from the hospital to AIDAVA are by default automatically added to AIDAVA, so that these documents are not appearing in the list of documents available for me to add to AIDAVA. (Patients shall not be asked to add to AIDAVA any documents which they do not know and cannot view/check.)	major	AC1124.1	All documents uploaded to AIDAVA by the hospital are automatically ingested to AIDAVA - Patients are not asked to "add to AIDAVA" any files they do not know and cannot view.
C0025	As a patient ingesting medical data into AIDAVA, I want the AIDAVA health data curation and publishing virtual assistant to check and handle duplicates automatically so that I do not need to bother	minor	AC0025.1	When the user request to ingest a data source, the system checks if the same data source content - (same data source, same patient, same provenance, same time period) - as a data source that has been already ingested
		minor	AC0025.2	If the data source to be ingested seems to be exactly the same, the system performs a DIFF on the content to confirm that the data sources are the same
		minor	AC0025.4	If the data source to be ingested is only partially the same (e.g. same type, but different patient, different content, ..) and the system cannot be 100% sure that it is a duplicate, it starts a dialogue and provides the user the option to specify: a) if this is indeed a duplicate and therefore stop ingestion; b) if this is not a duplicate, and go to next step in the curation process (with a risk to identify some duplicates in the content)

Requirement ID	Requirement	Severity (for G2)	Acceptance Criterion ID	Acceptance Criterion
C0041	As a 3rd-party app developer using the AIDAVA system, I want to be able to send new data if I get them (for instance longitudinal wearable data) so that I can enhance my data	major	AC0041.2	AIDAVA notifies the patient when new data is available for ingestion (i.e. when new data is available for adding to AIDAVA by patient) (= AC1106.1)
C0022	As a patient ingesting medical data into AIDAVA, I want to include information about my allergies in AIDAVA so that my doctor can see all relevant information at a glance	major	AC0022.1	The system allows to ingest information about a patient's allergies
C0024	As a patient ingesting medical data into AIDAVA, I want to see a checkmark within the AIDAVA health data curation and publishing virtual assistant (no separate email and no messaging!) signalling the data was well received by the AIDAVA health data curation and publishing virtual assistant so that I know ingestion of data to AIDAVA was successful	minor	AC0024.4	In case of an error icon, the user can click on the icon and see the error message with a description of the issue and proposed resolution
C1059	As a patient using AIDAVA I want to share my data in AIDAVA (including medical images) with a healthcare provider of my choice so that they can make accurate diagnoses (e.g. when I want to get a second opinion).	minor	AC1059.1	The DICOM metadata defined in the standard (e.g. for pathology) are mapped to the AIDAVA reference ontology
		minor	AC1059.2	Each site confirms in the DTS, the DICOM metadata that are considered as mandatory when transferring an image
		major	AC1059.3	The system allows to store mammography of BC patients (extract from local PACS/RIS system with patient consent) in a secure environment, linked to the patient PHKG.
		major	AC1059.4	The system allows to store cardiac echography of CVD patients (extract from local PACS/RIS system with patient consent) in a secure environment, linked to the patient PHKG. The image size will be 1-2 GB/patient.
		minor	AC1059.5 (AC0060.1)	When storing the medical image, the system provides a link to the patient PHKG to this medical image, and the DICOM metadata related to the image
		minor	AC1059.6	When storing the medical image, if mandatory (DICOM) metadata are missing the system starts a HITL dialogue

Requirement ID	Requirement	Severity (for G2)	Acceptance Criterion ID	Acceptance Criterion
C1073	As a site admin/site architect providing Master Data to AIDAVA, I want to automatically upload public information on health care providers (health care organisations and health care personnel) into the Master Data Repository of AIDAVA, so that my work is easier and less error-prone.	minor	AC1073.1	Whenever there is a public DB available, downloaded the content related to the site into AIDAV Master DB
C1074	As a site admin/site architect providing Master Data to AIDAVA, I want that in the user interface for entering master data all required fields are clearly marked (e.g. with *), so that I know which information must be provided by me.	minor	AC1074.1	There is a UI available to enter master data
C1075	As a site admin/site architect providing Master Data to AIDAVA, I want that in the user interface for entering master data every field, which is related to a value set, displays the potential value set in a dropdown list with the preferred value as default (e.g. address use = work), so that my work is easier and I understand better what input is required.	minor	AC1075.1	In the user interface for entering master data every field, which is related to a value set, displays the potential value set in a dropdown list with the preferred value as default (e.g. address use = work),
C1076	As a site admin/site architect providing Master Data to AIDAVA, I want that the value of v-card (.vcf file) should be assessed, so that I can upload the available hospital-staff-related data and my work is easier and less error-prone	minor	AC1076.1	For entering master data of persons, AIDAVA is able to handle v-card values (.vcf files)
C1078	As a site admin/site architect providing Master Data to AIDAVA, I want that when a synonym of an entity is found in the patient record that does not exist yet in the Master DB, the synonym should be added as "proposed synonym" into the Master DB, so that I could then decide to make it an officially accepted synonym.	minor	AC1078.1	entity deduplication should allow to identify double instance of the same entity and generate a synonym in the KG
		minor	AC1078.2	synonym should be added in the Master DB whenever identified in the KG
C1081	As a site admin/architect providing patient data from hospital to AIDAVA, I want that there is a mechanism for automatically checking the hospital-provided data (.csv files) before uploading these data to AIDAVA. This automatic data check should provide a report of the checking results to me (i.e. the responsible site architect) so that in case of issues with the .csv files these can be fixed by me (i.e. the responsible site architect).	major	AC1081.1	validator is checking the data file and the metadata file of each patient data ingested into the system; in case of failure a report is issued

Data Curation

26 functional requirements concerning data curation have been assessed in Phase 2 of Task 1.3 to be relevant for the AIDAVA prototype. For these 26 functional requirements in total 49 acceptance criteria have been defined.

Requirement ID	Requirement	Severity (for G2)	Acceptance Criterion ID	Acceptance Criterion
C0025	As a patient ingesting medical data into AIDAVA, I want the AIDAVA health data curation and publishing virtual assistant to check and handle duplicates automatically so that I do not need to bother	major	AC0025.5	The system includes a workflow for entity deduplication and this is working reliably.
		major	AC0025.6	In case of redundant data, the system tries to solve it automatically (e.g. master data matching and ranking)
		major	AC0025.7	In case of redundant data, and in case system cannot solve automatically (redundancies with lack of semantic), the system starts a HITL dialogue with the user providing the context (redundant data, data source of each data)
C0008	As an expert curator curating medical data in the AIDAVA, I want the application to save and store all the data I enter so that I can go at any time and search/view and if necessary change the already curated data	minor	AC0008.3	The system allows a specific user to visualize (within a table) all the actions he/she made on one data source for a given patient
C0056	As an expert curator using automatic data curation in AIDAVA, I want to have an automatic notification when there is an erroneous parameter during the data curation in order to avoid errors	blocking	AC0056.4a	In the HITL-dialogue, the question to the user is clear/straightforward (without domain-specific terminology).
		blocking	AC0056.4b	In the HITL-dialogue, the system provides contextual information to support the user.
C0042	As an expert curator helping AIDAVA with manual data curation, I want AIDAVA to offer me the option to answer the questions of the AIDAVA health data curation and publishing virtual assistant all together at a specific point in time (daily preferably) so that the rest of the time I can still proceed with my usual work	minor	AC0042.2	When there is an issue to be answered by a curator, the system checks if this is happening at the time where the curator mentioned he/she is available. If yes, the system initiates a HITL dialogue
		minor	AC0042.7	There is a small icon on the curator screen with the log of issues to be solved. When there is an open issue in the log, the icon changes colour/get a flag. (" you have got mail"?)

Requirement ID	Requirement	Severity (for G2)	Acceptance Criterion ID	Acceptance Criterion
		minor	AC0042.8	If the log of issue to be solved is not empty, at the available time mentioned by the curator, the system sends an email to tell him/her that there are issues to be solved
C0044	As an expert curator helping AIDAVA with manual data curation, I want the AIDAVA health data curation and publishing virtual assistant to give me answer options/suggestions so that I can quickly answer the AIDAVA health data curation and publishing virtual assistant's question	major	AC0044.1	As part of the HITL dialogue for expert curator AND for patient (-> AC0064.1+2, AC0066.2), the system provides different options to answer the question - including possibility to enter own answer (with format required for output, e.g. a number, a date, a code, ...to ensure it can be further processed)
C0045	As an expert curator helping AIDAVA with manual data curation, I want the AIDAVA health data curation and publishing virtual assistant to allow me to put in my own answer if the answer options provided by the AIDAVA health data curation and publishing virtual assistant do not cover the right answer so that I am not getting restricted by the AIDAVA health data curation and publishing virtual assistant	major	AC0045.1	=AC0044.1 (... including possibility to enter own answer...)
C0064	As a patient helping with data curation, I want the AIDAVA health data curation and publishing virtual assistant to provide me with suggestions of how to address the issue, which is raised by the AIDAVA health data curation and publishing virtual assistant, and in addition give me the option to make my own fix, if I find the suggestions provided by the AIDAVA health data curation and publishing virtual assistant are not appropriate/good, so that I can help the AIDAVA health data curation and publishing virtual assistant with clarifying ambiguities found in my data	major	AC0064.1	=AC0044.1 (system provides answer options...)
C0046	As an expert curator helping AIDAVA with manual data curation, if I don't know the answer to a question of the AIDAVA health data curation and publishing virtual assistant, I want to have the option to extract the question including the respective medical report(s) in an email so I can forward it to the doctor/expert of the respective field so that I don't have to write all the information by myself (e.g. which patient, which medical report of which date, in which line, what is the question, ...)	minor	AC0046.2	The AIDAVA system provides the curator the option to copy / paste the questions (and context) - so that he/she can include it in an email and forward the question and ask an expert to help with the curation task (in G2)

Requirement ID	Requirement	Severity (for G2)	Acceptance Criterion ID	Acceptance Criterion
C0052 & C0054	As an expert curator using automatic data curation in AIDAVA, I want the AIDAVA health data curation and publishing virtual assistant to proactively ask for help, - if medical reports are not clear or the information from different medical reports are contradicting so that I don't need to check for unclear medical reports by myself - when AIDAVA doesn't understand abbreviations, certain words, when there are similar diagnoses, double loaded files, confusing dates, or when a cell is empty so that I can open a separate view with the data for review	blocking	AC0052.1 & AC0054.1b	The system includes a list of data quality checks to check INCONSISTENCIES (in event/findings or in time) The system asks for human help when there are inconsistencies (such as contradicting diagnoses, confusing dates...)
		blocking	AC0054.1a	The system asks for human help when it is not sure about the meaning of an abbreviation/word, and there is need for deduplication
C1138	As a patient using AIDAVA, I want AIDAVA to correctly interpret and extract information from doctor's medical reports in local language which are often using abbreviations, ignoring punctuation and spelling rules and employing a lot of special terminology in their specific field, so that the content of my curated data is correctly reflecting the original data.	blocking	AC1138.1	AIDAVA correctly extracts information from medical reports related to the two therapeutic areas BC and CVD in a) Dutch language b) Estonian language c) German language.
		blocking	AC1138.3	AIDAVA correctly recognises specialized, domain-specific terminology in medical reports in Dutch/Estonian/German language.
		major	AC1138.4	AIDAVA correctly recognises information in (not handwritten) medical reports in Dutch/Estonian/German language, which do not strictly follow the language-specific punctuation and spelling rules.
		blocking	AC1138.2 (patient)	= AC0057.1 (<i>AIDAVA accurately recognises medical abbreviations in context</i>)
C0057	As a data user retrieving medical data from AIDAVA (and as a patient / curator using automatic data curation in AIDAVA), I want the AIDAVA health data curation and publishing virtual assistant to recognize medical abbreviations in the right context and put them in a consistent form so that the right records end up in the results.	major	AC0057.1-u (data user)	The system accurately recognises medical abbreviations in context (e.g., in a mammography report the abbreviation ACR stands for “ <i>American College of Radiology category</i> ” (i.e. indicates breast tissue density) rather than for “ <i>Amalgam Cement Restoration of tooth</i> ”)

Requirement ID	Requirement	Severity (for G2)	Acceptance Criterion ID	Acceptance Criterion
		blocking	AC0057.1-c (curator)	The system accurately recognises medical abbreviations in context
		major	AC0057.2	The system ensures correct coding of abbreviations (i.e. link a proper code to an abbreviation, a term or a set of terms)
C0058	As a data user retrieving medical data from AIDAVA, I want the AIDAVA health data curation and publishing virtual assistant to correctly recognize negations so that no information is misrepresented.	major	AC0058.1	The NLP tool supporting curation of free text document/narratives accurately identifies negations within the medical data and these extractions pass quality control mechanisms.
		major	AC0058.2	The Entity Linking tool supporting curation of small set of free text (within semi-structured data sources) accurately identifies negations within the medical data and ensures the representation of information is correct
C1104	As a patient, answering questions from AIDAVA, I want AIDAVA to extract dates of procedures/findings from the source data properly and preserve the context information (e.g. one date of a lab report is related to several measurements), so that patients receive no unnecessary questions.	blocking	AC1104.1	AIDAVA extracts temporal information (dates) from the source data properly, considering and preserving also the context (such as for example: one date given in a lab report is related to several measurements listed in that lab report).
C0059	As a data user retrieving medical data from AIDAVA, I want the AIDAVA health data curation and publishing virtual assistant to consider whether a finding/X-ray/lab-result was taken before or after a treatment so that I know whether a patient is suitable for a study or not.	minor	AC0059.1	The SHKG/PHKG includes the time stamp - captured in the data source - for each finding
		minor	AC0059.2b	b) there are DQ rules to check the appropriate temporal order of events
		minor	AC0059.3	AC1059.2 (<i>image must include a time stamp</i>) and AC1059.6 (<i>request if missing</i>)
C0062	As a patient helping with data curation, I expect the AIDAVA health data curation and publishing virtual assistant to make almost all curation work automatically so that I receive only very few questions (help requests) from the AIDAVA health data curation and publishing virtual assistant	major	AC0062.2	The system performs at least 70%-90% of the curation processes automatically.

Requirement ID	Requirement	Severity (for G2)	Acceptance Criterion ID	Acceptance Criterion
C0063	As a patient helping with data curation, I want to be able to see my different types of data, which I shall curate, in tabs (e.g. oncology, cardio, general health, etc.) so that I am not overwhelmed by a huge list of data to curate	minor	AC0063.1	The system provides different ways to filter the data sources to be curated (according to e.g. date, ingestion source, type of data source)
C0066	As a patient helping with data curation, I expect the AIDAVA virtual assistant to learn from my curation input (e.g. if I use specific units when curating lab results the AIDAVA health data curation and publishing virtual assistant will use as a default for all lab results I will curate, unless I indicate otherwise) so that I do not need to answer the same type of questions over and over again	major	AC0066.1	The system suggests an answer based on the user's previous answers to similar help requests
C1134	As a curator answering AIDAVA's questions, I want AIDAVA to learn from my answers so that I am not asked the same question several times.	major	AC1134.1	= AC0066.1 (<i>The system suggests an answer based on the user's previous answers to similar help requests</i>)
C0048	As an expert curator using the AIDAVA system, I want to be able to mark patients or questions from the AIDAVA health data curation and publishing virtual assistant with a colour scheme so that I know what my current status on the question is, (e.g. I want to mark a question where I have to ask the doctor to be able to answer it)	minor	AC0048.2	The system provides the expert curator and the patient (-> AC0065.3) the possibility to copy/paste the question at hand + context so that the user can decide to forward it to a medical expert (with their infrastructure of choice)
C0060	As a data user retrieving medical data from AIDAVA, I want the PHKG to be linked with medical images* of the patient so that I know which medical images* have been taken and can request access (* excluding histopathological whole slide images for the prototype)	minor	AC0060.1	=AC1059.5 (<i>linking DICOM images to PHKG</i>)
C0214	As a patient and as a curator helping AIDAVA with manual data curation, I want to get information where the data, regarding which the AIDAVA health data curation and publishing virtual assistant is asking me for curation help, comes from so that I can answer AIDAVA's questions more easily.	major	AC0214.2-p patient	When the patient is asked a question about a specific data item being curated, they can click on a button "provenance information"; and then the system displays the provenance information (metadata) in a human readable form.
		major	AC0214.2-c curator	When the expert curator is asked a question about a specific data item being curated, they can click on a button "provenance information"; and then the system displays the provenance information (metadata) in a human readable form.

Requirement ID	Requirement	Severity (for G2)	Acceptance Criterion ID	Acceptance Criterion
		minor	AC0214.6-p patient	= AC1139.1: <i>Whenever AIDAVA displays a source to a patient: In case the source was NOT a document but a CSV- and if a link to a PDF document is available in the DTS - the linked PDF document is displayed to the patient on demand</i> Note: explainability is not possible on the PDF!
		minor	AC0214.6-c curator	In case the source was NOT a document but a CSV- and if a link to a PDF document is available in the DTS - the linked PDF document is displayed to the expert curator on demand (e.g. lab reports are CSV format but the hospital provides a PDF rendering to the patients - this PDF rendering should be shown the expert curator). Note: explainability is not possible on the PDF!
C1088	As a patient / curator answering a question of AIDAVA (HITL dialogue), I want to see (on demand) the source and (if applicable) the relevant part of the source highlighted to which the question of AIDAVA is related, so that I can understand and answer the question more easily.	major	AC1088.1-p patient	If applicable: When displaying the source to the patient, the system highlights those part(s) of the source, to which the system's help request is related to.
		major	AC1088.1-c curator	If applicable: When displaying the source to the curator, the system highlights those part(s) of the source, to which the system's help request is related to.
C0297	As a patient ingesting medical data into AIDAVA, I want to have safeguarding checks in place to recognize whether the data/information was input correctly, and the AIDAVA health data curation and publishing virtual assistant shall tell me to review this information when there are obvious mistakes (e.g. when mistakenly uploaded a health document from another person) so that I can review and correct the mistake	blocking	AC0297.1b	If the content of a document has differences with regards to patient's name or birthdate, the system recognises this (consistency checks) and starts a HITL dialogue.
C1060	As a patient using AIDAVA I want to make sure that my medical images are of the best quality when I share them with a healthcare provider of my choice so that they can make accurate diagnoses.	minor	AC1060.1	The DICOM metadata are automatically curated and inserted into the PHKG

Requirement ID	Requirement	Severity (for G2)	Acceptance Criterion ID	Acceptance Criterion
		minor	AC1060.2	The system standardizes images and improves “quality” of the image and stores it into the secure AIDAVA server, linked to the patient PHKG - as a curated image. By improving quality, we mean - better contrast to more easily identify organs and tumour, - less noise and artefacts in the image, and - ability to depict small structures
		minor	AC1060.3	From a collection of medical image scans within a volume, the most pertinent scan that effectively displays the region of interest, will be identified as candidate for transfer
		minor	AC1060.4	The system transforms the identified candidate image of interest into a low volume PDF image for patient information (with explanation on findings); the PDF has a link to the original high-resolution image
		major	AC1060.5	The image available to the patient is of good quality (e.g. high resolution) so that it can be used to show it to a doctor for obtaining a second opinion.
C1072	As a patient, I want to see in my AIDAVA app the expert curator's answers to AIDAVA's questions concerning curation of my data/documents, so that I know what the curator has answered with respect to my health data.	major	AC1072.1	The expert curator's answers to a curation question (HITL) are shown in the patient's app.
		major	AC1133.2	In the AIDAVA app for patients, in requests for curation help (HITL) the relation to the section in the IPS is shown if applicable.
C1150	As a patient using AIDAVA to curate my "paper-format" medical documents which I have uploaded as a picture to MIDATA according to the guidelines, I want that the text, which is automatically extracted from the picture by AIDAVA, is of good quality so that it can be further processed and curated by AIDAVA.	major	AC1150.1	If a picture of a paper document, which is taken according to the guideline, is uploaded to AIDAVA, the text extracted from that picture is of good quality so that it can be further processed by AIDAVA without the patient having to re-type huge parts of the text.

User Interaction

51 functional requirements concerning user interaction have been assessed in Phase 2 of Task 1.3 to be relevant for the AIDAVA prototype. For these 51 functional requirements in total 88 acceptance criteria have been defined.

Requirement ID	Requirement	Severity (for G2)	Acceptance Criterion ID	Acceptance Criterion
C0090	As a patient helping with data curation, I want the AIDAVA health data curation and publishing virtual assistant to make it clear to me where and why my help is needed, if the AIDAVA health data curation and publishing virtual assistant found conflicting information, so that I can support the AIDAVA health data curation and publishing virtual assistant with improving my personal health data	major	AC0090.3	AIDAVA provides contextual information and explanation to support the user with answering the system's question: --> AC0214.4-p (show the source to which the system's question is related); --> AC1088.1-p (highlight those part(s) of the source to which the system's help request is related) --> AC1089.1-p (provenance information for this help request: at which step in the data curation process did this help request evolve, and which AIDAVA component was initiating this help request)
		major	AC0090.4	When asking a (IPS-relevant) question to the patient (HITL), AIDAVA makes it clear to the patient that answering this question is essential for the patient's IPS to be complete and correct so that the patient sees what this relates to.
C0080	As an expert curator helping AIDAVA with manual data curation, I expect the AIDAVA health data curation and publishing virtual assistant to provide clear questions and supporting information to help answer this question based on the context provided so that I do not have to check for additional information	major	AC0080.1	=AC0090.3 (When asking a question (HITL), AIDAVA provides contextual information...): --> AC0214.4-c (show the source to which the system's question is related); --> AC1088.1-c (highlight those part(s) of the source to which the system's help request is related) --> AC1089.1-c (provenance information for this help request...)
C0094	As a patient using the AIDAVA system, I want to be able to communicate with AIDAVA in a conversational manner (e.g. via a chatbot/live chat/hotline/e-mail address) so that the AIDAVA health data curation and publishing virtual assistant can be used on a smartphone on the browsers above 8% market share per platform (Android - Chrome, IOS - Safari).	major	AC0094.1	The system offers the option to communicate with AIDAVA with a conversational UI (example: chatbot)

Requirement ID	Requirement	Severity (for G2)	Acceptance Criterion ID	Acceptance Criterion
C0089	As a data user retrieving medical data from AIDAVA, I want to have a user-friendly UI So that I will not spend a lot of time to retrieve the data	minor	AC0089.1	The system gives feedback to the user if the level of reliability is appropriate.
C0097	As a patient using the AIDAVA system, I want to be able to communicate with a human support via chat so that I can use my usual fast communication channels	minor	AC0097.1	The system offers the option to communicate with a human support via chat
C0234	As a patient using the AIDAVA system, I want the AIDAVA health data curation and publishing virtual assistant to provide different language options to communicate with the AIDAVA health data curation and publishing virtual assistant so that everyone can choose their mother language	blocking	AC0234.2b	The MIDATA user interface is available in Dutch. <i>(Provision of MIDATA services in the Netherlands is subject to accept of an amendment to the grant agreement and respective additional funding)</i>
C1066	As a patient during the profile verification when I see some incorrect information, I want to specify what is incorrect in the profile information displayed to me by AIDAVA, so that it can be corrected.	blocking	AC1066.1	When AIDAVA asks the patient to verify their profile, the patient can indicate that this profile is not correct.
		blocking	AC1066.2	When a patient indicates that their profile is not correct, they can edit their profile information to correct it.
C1067	As a patient using AIDAVA, I want AIDAVA to give me the possibility to view my curated data in human-readable form, so that I can (on demand) see my curated data and check what is in my curated data.	major	AC1067.1	In the AIDAVA app, the patient has got the possibility to ask for display of the content of their curated data (PHKG) anytime.
		major	AC1067.2	On demand of the patient, AIDAVA displays the content of their PHKG in human-readable form
C1083	As a patient I want that AIDAVA displays my patient-answered QoL questionnaire in human-readable format, so that I can see and understand what is in this document, if I want to.	major	AC1083.1	AIDAVA displays (on demand) the patient-answered QoL questionnaire in human-readable format (not json-format, as in G1)
C1084	As a data user (physician) looking at an output calculated by AIDAVA (e.g. BC registry metric, SMART score), I want AIDAVA to provide me (on demand) information of how AIDAVA calculated this output (formula + values of the variables), so that I can better understand how AIDAVA arrived at this output.	minor	AC1084.1a	When displaying the value of a BC metric calculated by the system, AIDAVA displays (on demand) the general mathematical formula according to which this BC metric was calculated.

Requirement ID	Requirement	Severity (for G2)	Acceptance Criterion ID	Acceptance Criterion
		minor	AC1084.1b	When displaying the general mathematical formula according to which a BC metric was calculated, AIDAVA shows for each of the variables in this formula the values (derived from the curated data) for the calculation of this specific value of the BC metric.
C1085	As a data user (physician) looking at the SMART score and seeing the formula (including the values of the variables) that AIDAVA used to calculate this output, I want AIDAVA to show me (on demand) for each of the values used in the formula the provenance information, i.e. the source and the transformation steps of that data element from the moment it was ingested into the system up to the moment it was used for calculating the output, so that I understand how AIDAVA arrived at this output	minor	AC1085.1a	When displaying the value of the SMART score calculated by the system, AIDAVA displays (on demand) the general mathematical formula according to which this SMART score was calculated.
		minor	AC1085.1b	When displaying the mathematical formula according to which the SMART score for a patient was calculated, AIDAVA shows for each of the variables in this formula the values (derived from the curated data) used for the calculation of this specific value of the SMART score.
		major	AC1085.2	When displaying the values of the variables used for calculation of the SMART score, AIDAVA displays for each of these values (on demand) the provenance information, i.e. the source and the transformation steps of that data element from the moment it was ingested into AIDAVA up to the moment it was used for calculation of the SMART score.
C1086	As a patient / curator / data user looking at the IPS displayed by AIDAVA, I want to see (on demand) provenance information for each element in the IPS (i.e. the source of this specific data element in the IPS as well as the "journey of that data element in AIDAVA"), so that I can understand how this data element was derived (i.e. from which source it was extracted, by which actor it was processed and what was the result of this processing).	major	AC1086.1	= AC0225.3 (for patient, expert curator, and data user)

Requirement ID	Requirement	Severity (for G2)	Acceptance Criterion ID	Acceptance Criterion
		major	AC1086.2	AIDAVA displays (on demand) information regarding which input (source) documents were used and which input (source) documents were not used for the creation of the IPS.
C1087	As a patient looking at the IPS displayed by MIDATA, I want to see (on demand) provenance information for each element in the IPS (i.e. the source of this specific data element in the IPS as well as the "journey of that data element in AIDAVA"), so that I can understand how this data element was derived (i.e. from which source it was extracted, by which actor it was processed and what was the result of this processing).	major	AC1087.1	For each data element displayed in the IPS, MIDATA shows (on demand) provenance information in human-readable form: a) source of this data element; if applicable highlighting that part of the source, where the data element was extracted from; b) curation process of this data element in AIDAVA including the involved actors and their tasks;
		major	AC1087.2	When showing the IPS, MIDATA displays (on demand) information regarding which input (source) documents were used for the creation of the IPS.
C1089	As a patient /curator answering a question of AIDAVA (HITL dialogue), I want to see (on demand) at which step in the data curation process this question evolved (What was AIDAVA trying to do with my data when this question came up? Which component of AIDAVA raised the question?), so that I can better understand why AIDAVA asks that question and why my input is needed.	minor	AC1089.1-p patient	AIDAVA displays (on demand) in human-readable form provenance information for a curation-question (HITL): a) description in lay language of the step in the curation process (i.e. activity performed by AIDAVA) when this question came up b) component of AIDAVA, which was initiating this question.
		minor	AC1089.1-c curator	AIDAVA displays (on demand) in human-readable form provenance information for a curation-question (HITL): a) description in lay language of the step in the curation process (i.e. activity performed by AIDAVA) when this question came up b) component initiating this question.
C1090	As a patient / curator seeing that curation of a document is finished (i.e. when AIDAVA displays the status "curated"), I want to see on demand the result of the curation (i.e. which information has been extracted from this document and included into the curated data/PHKG), so that I can check what AIDAVA has done if I want to.	major	AC1090.1-p patient	= AC0298.3b (<i>system shows for a curated source document on demand the curated data, which have been extracted from that source</i>);

Requirement ID	Requirement	Severity (for G2)	Acceptance Criterion ID	Acceptance Criterion
		major	AC1090.1-c curator	= AC0290.3 (<i>system shows for a curated source document on demand the curated data, which have been extracted from that source</i>);
C1091	As a patient / curator seeing that curation of a document is finished (i.e. when AIDAVA displays the status "curated"), I want to see on demand what happened to this document during curation (i.e. curation process incl. involved actors...), so that I can see what AIDAVA has done if I want to.	minor	AC1091.1-p patient	AIDAVA displays (on demand) for a curated document the provenance (i.e. steps of the curation process + actors involved) in human readable form.
		minor	AC1091.1-c curator	AIDAVA displays (on demand) for a curated document the provenance (i.e. steps of the curation process + actors involved) in human readable form.
C1092	As a patient seeing the results of curation, I want to have the possibility to tell AIDAVA to not include a certain piece of curated information into my PHKG, so that I can have control.	minor	AC1092.1	When displaying curated data (SKG/PHKG) to a patient, AIDAVA provides the patient the possibility to flag any of these data items included in the curated data as "not to be used". Data items marked by the patient as "not to be used" are not further used by AIDAVA (i.e. not published and not used for any calculations done by AIDAVA)
C1094	As a provider of AIDAVA, I want to have the possibility to test the application thoroughly before I provide this solution to patients, so that I know what my patients will get.	major	AC1094.1	each module has been tested independently first and then tested with the overall system as part of integration testing
C1096	As a patient / curator looking at a source document displayed by AIDAVA, I want AIDAVA to provide me (on demand) with human understandable provenance information of this source document/data in plain language (no codes, no "technical" terms), so that I know when this document was created and who is responsible for the content.	minor	AC1096.1-p patient	AIDAVA displays (on demand) provenance information of a source document in plain language, including (at least) the creation date and the author (institution) of that source document.
		major	AC1096.1-c curator	AIDAVA displays (on demand) provenance information of a source document in plain language, including (at least) the creation date and the author (institution) of that source document.
C1097	As a data user, I want AIDAVA to display to a data user (clinician) only those patients, who shall be accessible to them, so that they do not see patients who are not accessible to them.	blocking	AC1097.1	AIDAVA shows to a data user (clinician) only those patients, who shall be accessible to them. No other patients are visible to them.

Requirement ID	Requirement	Severity (for G2)	Acceptance Criterion ID	Acceptance Criterion
C1100	As a patient, I want the AIDAVA app to ask me the "medical & digital literacy" questions when I activate my AIDAVA account (Not separately e.g. in a paper questionnaire), so that it is clear that my answers to these questions form part of my user profile in AIDAVA.	minor	AC1100.1	Asking the patient to answer the digital & medical literacy questions is integrated in the AIDAVA app as part of the process for account activation.
		minor	AC1100.2	When AIDAVA asks a patient to answer the digital & medical literacy questions, a clear and easy to understand explanation in plain language of how the results of this questionnaire will be used in AIDAVA is provided to the patient.
		minor	AC1100.3	The patient's answers to the digital & medical literacy questions are displayed in the patient's user profile on demand.
C1102	As a patient asking AIDAVA to show me the source related to a curation question or the source of a data item in AIDAVA's output, I want AIDAVA to show me on demand the pdf-file of a source document (if available) in addition to the .csv file, so that I can better understand what is in the source file since .csv files uploaded from hospital are not understandable to patients.	minor	AC1102.1	= AC1139.1: <i>Whenever AIDAVA displays a source to a patient: In case the source was NOT a document but a CSV- and if a link to a PDF document is available in the DTS - the linked PDF document is displayed to the patient on demand ...</i>
C1105	As a patient answering AIDAVA's questions, I want AIDAVA to recognise when I've finished answering a question (i.e. when I've confirmed my answer replayed by AIDAVA) independently of providing an optional comment or clicking on "Skip comment", so that the system does not keep displaying "Waiting for patient" for questions already answered.	major	AC1105.1-p patient	In the HITL dialogue, AIDAVA recognises that the patient has finished answering a question as soon as the patient confirms their answer replayed by AIDAVA. Providing a comment is optional and clicking on "skip comment" is not needed to successfully finish a HITL dialogue.
		minor	AC1105.1-c curator	In the HITL dialogue, AIDAVA recognises that the expert curator has finished answering a question as soon as the expert curator confirms their answer replayed by AIDAVA. Providing a comment is optional and clicking on "skip comment" is not needed to successfully finish a HITL dialogue.

Requirement ID	Requirement	Severity (for G2)	Acceptance Criterion ID	Acceptance Criterion
C1106	As a patient using AIDAVA for data curation, I want to see on my AIDAVA dashboard when there are documents available/waiting for being added to AIDAVA, so that I can add these documents to AIDAVA.	major	AC1106.1	AIDAVA indicates in the patient's app when documents are available for the patient to be added to AIDAVA.
C1107	As a patient / curator / data user looking at a source document (pdf) displayed by AIDAVA, I want to have the possibility to zoom the source document displayed by AIDAVA, so that I can read what is written in the source document (otherwise the text is too tiny to be readable)	major	AC1107.1-p patient	When AIDAVA displays a source document, the user is provided with the possibility to zoom this source document (so that the text becomes readable).
		major	AC1107.1-c curator	When AIDAVA displays a source document, the user is provided with the possibility to zoom this source document (so that the text becomes more readable).
		major	AC1107.1-u data user	When AIDAVA displays a source document, the user is provided with the possibility to zoom this source document (so that the text becomes more readable).
C1108	As a patient / curator answering AIDAVA's questions when AIDAVA asks me to check an OCR-extracted text, I want that the "edit window" where the OCR-extracted text is shown by AIDAVA is showing a big portion of the text rather than only a few lines, so that I can more easily recognise which part of the source text is displayed.	major	AC1108.1-p patient	When AIDAVA asks a patient (HITL) to check and correct an OCR-extracted text, the "edit window" is large so that 7 or more lines of text can be displayed in easy-to-read font size.
		major	AC1108.1-c curator	When AIDAVA asks a curator (HITL) to check and correct an OCR-extracted text, the "edit window" is large so that 7 or more lines of text can be displayed in easy-to-read font size.
C1109	As a patient / curator answering AIDAVA's questions when AIDAVA asks me to check an OCR-extracted text, I want that it is possible to easily scroll in the "edit window" where the OCR-extracted text is shown by AIDAVA, so that I can easily check and correct the extracted text.	major	AC1109.1-p patient	When AIDAVA asks a patient (HITL) to check and correct an OCR-extracted text, AIDAVA provides the user the possibility to easily scroll in the "edit window", where the OCR-extracted text is displayed.
		major	AC1109.1-c curator	When AIDAVA asks a curator (HITL) to check and correct an OCR-extracted text, AIDAVA provides the user the possibility to easily scroll in the "edit window", where the OCR-extracted text is displayed.

Requirement ID	Requirement	Severity (for G2)	Acceptance Criterion ID	Acceptance Criterion
C1122	As a patient / curator answering AIDAVA's questions when AIDAVA asks me to check an OCR-extracted text, I want AIDAVA to display in the "edit window" the extracted text starting with the first "text"-lines (any preceding "blank" lines skipped), so that I do not have the impression that the "edit window" is empty.	major	AC1122.1-p patient	When AIDAVA asks a patient (HITL) to check and correct an OCR-extracted text, the OCR-extracted text is displayed in the "edit window" in such a way that the first text-lines are visible (not only "blank" lines!).
		major	AC1122.1-c curator	When AIDAVA asks a curator (HITL) to check and correct an OCR-extracted text, the OCR-extracted text is displayed in the "edit window" in such a way that the first text-lines are visible (not only "blank" lines!).
C1123	As a patient / curator answering AIDAVA's questions when AIDAVA asks me to check an OCR-extracted text, I want AIDAVA to display in the "edit window" the extracted text formatted similar to the original text rather than show it as a bulk text, so that it is easier for me to recognise the corresponding text-parts in the original and extracted texts.	major	AC1123.1-p patient	When AIDAVA asks a patient (HITL) to check and correct an OCR-extracted text, the OCR-extracted text is displayed in the "edit window" in such a way that line-breaks are preserved so that it resembles better the formatting of the original text.
		major	AC1123.1-c curator	When AIDAVA asks a curator (HITL) to check and correct an OCR-extracted text, the OCR-extracted text is displayed in the "edit window" in such a way that line-breaks are preserved so that it resembles better the formatting of the original text.
C1110	As a patient / curator / data user seeing a quality score displayed by AIDAVA, I want to get (on demand) an explanation of the quality score (What does it mean? How is it derived? What implications does it have if it is not optimal? How can it be improved?), so that I can understand it.	major	AC1110.1-p patient	Whenever AIDAVA displays a quality score, the patient has the possibility to get (on demand) explanations regarding this quality score, including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What does this quality score tell the user? - How is this quality score derived by AIDAVA? - Why is this quality score not optimal? (Where are the (remaining) errors in the data?) - What implications does it have if this quality score is not optimal? - How could this quality score be improved? (How can the (remaining) errors in the data be fixed?)

Requirement ID	Requirement	Severity (for G2)	Acceptance Criterion ID	Acceptance Criterion
		major	AC1110.1-c curator	Whenever AIDAVA displays a quality score, the curator has the possibility to get (on demand) explanations regarding this quality score, including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What does this quality score tell the user? - How is this quality score derived by AIDAVA? - Why is this quality score not optimal? (Where are the (remaining) errors in the data?) - What implications does it have if this quality score is not optimal? - How could this quality score be improved? (How can the (remaining) errors in the data be fixed?)
		major	AC1110.1-u data user	Whenever AIDAVA displays a quality score, the data user has the possibility to get (on demand) explanations regarding this quality score, including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What does this quality score tell the user? - How is this quality score derived by AIDAVA? - Why is this quality score not optimal? (Where are the (remaining) errors in the data?) - What implications does it have if this quality score is not optimal? - How could this quality score be improved? (How can the (remaining) errors in the data be fixed?)
C1114	As a patient willing to upload a picture of a medical document (which I have got on paper) to MIDATA, I want to get a clear explanation and guidance of how I should take the picture from the paper document and what I need to take care of or what I need to avoid, so that the uploaded picture can be processed by AIDAVA.	major	AC1114.1	In the MIDATA app there is clear guidance provided to a patient of how to take a picture of a paper document in such a way that the uploaded picture will be of sufficient quality for curation by AIDAVA.
C1115	As a patient answering AIDAVA's questions, I want AIDAVA to formulate the question in plain language using easy to understand terminology and avoiding complicated medical and technical terms (such as "file identifier", "procedure", "code"...), so that I can easily understand the question.	blocking	AC1115.1	HITL: AIDAVA's questions addressed to a patient are clear and formulated in plain language using easy to understand terminology and avoiding complicated technical terms.
		major	AC1115.2	HITL: AIDAVA's questions addressed to a patient are suitable for the patient's level of medical literacy.

Requirement ID	Requirement	Severity (for G2)	Acceptance Criterion ID	Acceptance Criterion
C1116	As a patient using AIDAVA, I want AIDAVA to have a reward system in place, so that I can more easily keep engaged with AIDAVA.	major	AC1116.1a	AIDAVA provides motivation to the patient by showing a) how the quality score of their medical file (SKG/PHKG) improves through their answering of questions (HITL) (--> see C1148)
		major	AC1116.1b	AIDAVA provides motivation to the patient by showing b) a clear overview of the remaining errors and who is going to fix these.
C1118	As a patient using AIDAVA, I want AIDAVA's user interfaces and dialogues available in proper translation to my local language and consistently following my selected language, so that I can easily understand it.	blocking	AC1118.1	In the patient's AIDAVA app, all UI elements and texts are displayed in the language selected by the patient.
		blocking	AC1118.2	In the patient's AIDAVA app, all UI elements and texts are easy to understand and meaningful.
C1119	As a patient using AIDAVA, I want that the displayed names of the documents available for me to curate in AIDAVA are meaningful, so that I can understand what these files are about.	major	AC1119.1	Patient's AIDAVA app: In the list of documents available for adding to AIDAVA and in the list of documents available for curation, the title of the document is displayed (in addition to the filename) for all documents where a title is available (e.g. the title provided by the patient when uploading a document through the HDI)
		major	AC1119.2	The quality-of-life questionnaire is listed with the same (meaningful!) name, both in the MIDATA and the AIDAVA app.
C1120	As a patient using AIDAVA, I want to have the possibility to rename the documents after upload to AIDAVA or at least change the displayed name of these documents, so that I can give meaningful names that give a clue regarding the origin and content of the respective document.	minor	AC1120.1	AIDAVA provides the patient the possibility to edit/change the display name of documents uploaded to AIDAVA.
C1121	As a patient using AIDAVA, I want AIDAVA to sort (by default or on demand) the list of documents available for curation in such a way that the most recently uploaded documents appear at the top of the list, so that I can have a better overview of my documents which need to be curated.	minor	AC1121	AIDAVA provides the possibility to sort the list of documents available for curation by ingestion date (so that the most recently uploaded documents appear at the top of the list).

Requirement ID	Requirement	Severity (for G2)	Acceptance Criterion ID	Acceptance Criterion
C1125	As a patient / curator answering AIDAVA's questions, when AIDAVA asks for a missing date I want to have the possibility to enter mm/yyyy if the exact date (i.e. the day) is not known, so that I can provide at least the information about mm/yyyy instead of no information at all.	major	AC1125.1-p patient	HITL: When a user is asked to provide a date, AIDAVA allows entering information regarding the year (yyyy) and month (mm) and skipping information regarding the day (dd), if the user cannot provide this information.
		major	AC1125.1-c curator	HITL: When a user is asked to provide a date, AIDAVA allows entering information regarding the year (yyyy) and month (mm) and skipping information regarding the day (dd), if the user cannot provide this information.
C1127	As a patient / curator answering AIDAVA's questions, when I recognise that AIDAVA has made a mistake (e.g. when AIDAVA asks for "date of amalgam restoration of tooth" while curating a mammography report), I want to have the possibility to give feedback that AIDAVA has made a mistake and stop AIDAVA from including that data item into the PHKG. Ideally, the AIDAVA system should learn from my feedback to avoid such mistakes in future data curation.	blocking	AC1127.1-p patient	In the HITL dialogue the patient is provided with the possibility to indicate that AIDAVA has made a mistake.
		major	AC1127.1-c curator	In the HITL dialogue the expert curator is provided with the possibility to indicate that AIDAVA has made a mistake.
		major	AC1127.2-p patient	When a patient indicates (during HITL) that AIDAVA has made a mistake, the system displays the curated data items related to the respective HITL help request and provides the patient the possibility to mark the respective data item(s) not correctly extracted from the source by AIDAVA as "error". Data items marked by the patient as "error" are not integrated into the patient's PHKG.
		major	AC1127.2-c curator	When the expert curator indicates (during HITL) that AIDAVA has made a mistake, the system displays the curated data items related to the respective HITL help request and provides the expert curator the possibility to mark the respective data item(s) not correctly extracted from the source by AIDAVA as "error". Data items marked by the expert curator as "error" are not integrated into the patient's PHKG.

Requirement ID	Requirement	Severity (for G2)	Acceptance Criterion ID	Acceptance Criterion
C1128	As a patient / curator answering AIDAVA's questions, I want AIDAVA to use in the questions the same terms as written in the source data, so that I can more easily understand what the question is about and more easily find the respective information in the source data. e.g. when the measurement of <i>LDH</i> is mentioned in a lab report, AIDAVA should not ask for ' <i>missing date of Laktatdehydrogenase procedure</i> '	minor*	AC1128.1-p patient	In the system's question (HITL) the same term (e.g. for a substance measured in the lab, a procedure, a diagnosis, etc.) is used as in the source document. (*Note: This acceptance criterium can be considered as minor if and only if AIDAVA clearly indicates the <u>part</u> of the source document the question is related to)
		minor*	AC1128.1-c curator	In the system's question (HITL) the same term (e.g. for a substance measured in the lab, a procedure, a diagnosis, etc.) is used as in the source document. (*Note: This acceptance criterium can be considered as minor only if AIDAVA clearly indicates the <u>part</u> of the source the question is related to)
C1130	As a patient / curator answering AIDAVA's questions, I want to keep the source file visible while answering AIDAVA's questions, so that I can see the document and the related questions next to each other.	major	AC1130.1-p patient	During HITL dialogue, AIDAVA displays (on demand) the related source document. By default, this view of the source document is displayed (next to the HITL dialogues) as long as the user is answering related system questions. The user has the possibility to manually close the source document view anytime.
		major	AC1130.1-c curator	During HITL dialogue, AIDAVA displays (on demand) the related source document. By default, this view of the source document is displayed (next to the HITL dialogues) as long as the user is answering related system questions. The user has the possibility to manually close the source document view anytime.
C1131	As a patient / curator answering AIDAVA's questions (HITL dialogue), I want AIDAVA to suggest date formats aligned with my selected language (e.g. in Estonia/Austria/Netherlands the format should be dd.mm.yyyy), so that it is easier for me to provide a date and I am not confused.	major	AC1131.1-p patient	When asking a user to provide a date, AIDAVA suggests a date format aligned with the user's selected language.
		major	AC1131.1-c curator	When asking a user to provide a date, AIDAVA suggests a date format aligned to the user's selected language.

Requirement ID	Requirement	Severity (for G2)	Acceptance Criterion ID	Acceptance Criterion
C1132	As a patient / curator answering AIDAVA's questions (HITL), when entering a comment, I want AIDAVA to allow in the comment field basic text formatting such as e.g. line breaks, so that I can more easily formulate my feedback/thoughts.	major	AC1132.1-p patient	In the input fields, where users are supposed to add comments/feedback, AIDAVA provides the possibility to introduce line-breaks in the common way (i.e. by using the "enter"-key)
		minor	AC1132.1-c curator	In the input fields, where users are supposed to add comments/feedback, AIDAVA provides the possibility to introduce line-breaks in the common way (i.e. by using the "enter"-key)
C1136	As a patient starting to use AIDAVA, I want to receive easy-to-understand recommendations for how I can contribute to increasing security (e.g., using a sufficiently long and complex password, using multi-factor authentication...)	minor	AC1136.1	When a patient activates their account, AIDAVA provides suggestions for increasing security, e.g. regarding choice of a secure password.
C1137	As a patient using AIDAVA, I want to receive meaningful error messages, so that I can understand what is wrong or why the system is not working as expected and (if applicable) what I can do to recover from an error. (e.g., when my session ends the system should notify me and send me back to the home-screen instead of displaying the error message "Cannot access resource.")	major	AC1137.1	Error messages displayed by AIDAVA to a patient are easily understandable without using complex technical terms and provide (if applicable) clear instructions of how to recover from the error.
C1139	As a patient using AIDAVA, I want AIDAVA to show me documents rather than tables, so that I can more easily read and understand the source files displayed by AIDAVA. (The natural source of information for a patient is a document not a table.)	minor	AC1139.1	Whenever AIDAVA displays a source to a patient: In case the source was NOT a pdf-document but a CSV- and if a link to a PDF document is available in the DTS - the linked PDF document is displayed to the patient on demand (e.g. lab reports are CSV format but the hospital provides a PDF rendering to the patients). Note: explainability is not possible on the PDF!
C1140	As a patient using AIDAVA, I want that the information provided to me by AIDAVA is adjusted to my skills and technical background, so that I can easily understand the information.	major	AC1140.1	Information/explanations provided by AIDAVA to the patient are in plain language and easy to understand by people with a low level of digital literacy.
C1142	As a patient curating my data and providing input to AIDAVA (HITL), I want to have the possibility to easily undo an action such as for example deleting part of the text I've provided in a comment field, so that I can easily correct my input to AIDAVA.	major	AC1142.1	Patients are provided the possibility to easily remove/change parts of their text, while they are typing text in a comment field.

Requirement ID	Requirement	Severity (for G2)	Acceptance Criterion ID	Acceptance Criterion
C1093	As a curator seeing the results of curation, I want to have the possibility to flag a certain piece of curated information as "erroneous" if I spot an error in that curated information.	major	AC1093.1	= AC0202.1 (<i>system provides a feature to report errors found in the data</i>)
C1148	As a patient using AIDAVA for curation of my health data, I want to see how the quality of my data has improved through curation, so that I can see the results of my curation efforts as a motivation to further use AIDAVA.	major	AC1148.1	AIDAVA displays a quality score of the patient's data at the start of curation and updates that quality score after each curation input of the patient, so that the patient sees the effect of their effort on data quality.

Data Publishing

23 functional requirements concerning data publishing have been assessed in Phase 2 of Task 1.3 to be relevant for the AIDAVA prototype. For these 23 functional requirements in total 46 acceptance criteria have been defined.

Requirement ID	Requirement	Severity (for G2)	Acceptance Criterion ID	Acceptance Criterion
C0131	As a data user assessing AIDAVA / evaluating results, I want AIDAVA to automatically calculate the SMART Risk Score (based on its data) and the time the AIDAVA virtual assistant took to calculate it so that I have the data I need to compare with manual work	blocking	AC0131.2b	In case, a mandatory value for calculation of the SMART risk score is missing, the missing information is asked to the physician; this information is stored in the PHKG
		blocking	AC0131.5	When the system displays the SMART risk score the data user has access to an icon which allows to display the entire formula and the value used by AIDAVA in each of the variables
		minor	AC0131.6	When the system displays the SMART risk score - when clicking on a variable, the user can see how this variable was obtained (data source and transformation)

Requirement ID	Requirement	Severity (for G2)	Acceptance Criterion ID	Acceptance Criterion
C0162 & C0146	<p>As a patient wanting to get out my data from AIDAVA, I want to get out my curated data from the AIDAVA system in Machine-readable electronic format so that I can have all my data back (e.g. before I delete my account = C0199).</p> <p>As a patient having my data in AIDAVA, I want the AIDAVA health data curation and publishing virtual assistant to extract my IPS (international patient summary) in machine-readable electronic format for further use</p>	major	AC0162.1	The system allows the patient to extract the IPS from the PHKG + related metadata (provenance of source + computer/curator traceability).
		blocking	AC0162.2b	The patient IPS code is sent to HDI by AIDAVA.
		minor	AC0162.3 patient	The system allows the patient to download the full (machine-readable) PHKG
C0173	As a data user and as a 3rd-party app developer retrieving medical data from AIDAVA for my app, I want to retrieve structured and consistent data (that was originally unstructured) so that I can use the structured data	blocking	AC0173.1b	The system provides quality data as defined in the following metrics: <i>(TBD after we finalize description of the metrics related to the DQ label of the 4 dimensions)</i>
C0111	As a data user retrieving medical data from AIDAVA, I want to see <u>personal information</u> of the patient (in scope of the use cases of AIDAVA) when I am the treating physician of the patient so that I can do my job more efficiently	major	AC0111.1b	As a physician I can see the list of the patients assigned to me in the AIDAVA system; the list indicates <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - (a) the status of data ingested/curated - (d) an icon with the availability of curated images - (e) The patients that are not assigned to me (i.e. the patients that should not be accessible for me) are not visible to me
		major	AC0111.1c	As a physician when I click on the patient in my list I want to access their IPS.... (THIS REQUIRES consent from the patient when there is no ongoing treatment; (Note: in the study this is granted through ICF but NOT for PRODUCT)
		minor	AC0111.8	For ALL physicians - publishing/data user screen. When clicking on the IMAGE icon on patient name in the list of patients, the physician has access to the patient image through a DICOM viewer (DicomWebViewer) for the selected patient (after checking authorization of access)

Requirement ID	Requirement	Severity (for G2)	Acceptance Criterion ID	Acceptance Criterion
C0112 & C0124	<p>As a data user when considering to access medical data through AIDAVA, I want to have the level of the data structure details so that I can have access to data in a patient specific level</p> <p>As a data user retrieving medical data from AIDAVA, I want to retrieve structured data as much as possible so that the data I retrieve are easy and handy to use</p>	minor	AC0112.1	G2: The system allows to specify a query within the PHKG to retrieve one or more patients based on the selected criteria
C0113	As a data user/clinician when retrieving medical data from AIDAVA, I want to have the option to select to see and retrieve anonymized data so that I can make reports, data analytics and research without having to take responsibility for identifiable patient data	major	AC0113.2	The system allows to extract the predefined list of data elements from the BC PHKG to generate the local BC clinical registry (in a RDF format), in each site
		major	AC0113.3	The system is able to compute Metric 1 for BC use case from the BC registry (see study protocol - section 3.2.1) - in each site
		major	AC0113.4	The system is able to compute Metric 2 for BC use case from the BC registry (see study protocol - section 3.2.1) 0 in each site
		major	AC0113.5	The system is able to compute Metric 3 for BC use case from the BC registry (see study protocol - section 3.2.1) - in each site
		major	AC0113.6	The system is able to fire a query - as defined in AC0113.3, AC0113.4 and AC0113.5) - in each site and to consolidate the result for the user
		major	AC0113.7	For G2. The system provides the user the possibility to request from the system how it computed the BC use case metrics (provenance of data)
C0114	As a data user retrieving medical data from AIDAVA, I want to retrieve data from several patients at once so that I have access to a large-scale dataset that can be used for several purposes including research	major	AC0114.1	AC0113.2

Requirement ID	Requirement	Severity (for G2)	Acceptance Criterion ID	Acceptance Criterion
C0176	As an HDI retrieving medical data from AIDAVA, I want my account holders to be able to have a copy of the PHKG in their HDI personal health account, in addition to the structured IPS data so that the account holders can put the PHKG to secondary use, in the sense of patient empowerment, sovereignty, and informational self-determination.	major	AC0176.2 (HDI)	Patients receive a copy of their PHKG into their personal HDI account in RDF format
		blocking	AC0176.3	The system needs to produce a full integrated PHKG containing the curated data from one individual patient as the representation of the patient's longitudinal health record
C1098	As a patient, I want to receive a copy of my PHKG into my HDI account, so that I can have my curated data in electronic format.	minor	AC1098.1 (patient)	= AC0176.2 (<i>Patients receive a copy of their PHKG into their personal HDI account</i>)
C0128	As a data user/clinician retrieving medical data from AIDAVA, I want the name of the patient and date of the results being presented always be visible so that I am always sure that I am looking at the right data/results and therefore I trust the information	minor	AC0128.1b	= AC0111.1c (<i>...physician has access to IPS of patient assigned to them...</i>)
--> =C0146 (extract IPS)		major	AC0199.1b	The system provides the patient the possibility to download their IPS in machine readable format. --> see AC0162.1
C1061	As a patient using AIDAVA I want AIDAVA to make sure that my physician can easily access my medical image	major	AC1061.1	=AC0111.8 (<i>the clinician assigned as data user to the patient in AIDAVA can click on "image icon" ... and has access to the patient's image through DICOM viewer</i>)
C1079	As a (BC) patient, I want to have the possibility to view my mammograms in AIDAVA, if clinicians agree, so that I can see my mammogram if I want to.	major	AC1079.1	AIDAVA provides the patient the possibility to view their mammograms uploaded to AIDAVA.
C1080	As a (CVD) patient, I want to have the possibility to view my echocardiograms in AIDAVA, if clinicians agree, so that I can see my echocardiograms if I want to.	major	AC1080.1	AIDAVA provides the patient the possibility to view their echocardiograms uploaded to AIDAVA.
C1070	As a data user (clinician) I want AIDAVA to show me the local BC registry in a human-readable format.	major	AC1070.1	From a predefined list of data elements - composing the Breast Cancer Registry - as extract from the PHKG (see AC0113.2), the system stores this information in csv-format in an OMOP compliant syntax

Requirement ID	Requirement	Severity (for G2)	Acceptance Criterion ID	Acceptance Criterion
		major	AC1070.2	The data user (clinician) is able to display the content of the BC registry
		minor	AC1070.3	While storing the data elements in the Breast Cancer registry in XLS, the system also stores the metadata: (see example below - G2 should have at least 1, 2, 3, 4a, 5, 6, 7) 1. Number of patients 2. Age (average and range) 3. Tumour size (range and average) 4. Tumour stage (T), lymph node metastases (N), distant metastases status (M): 4 a. # or % of patients by stage (T1 vs T2 vs T3 vs T4) 4 b. Presence of lymph node metastases (N0 /others) 4 c. Presence of distant metastases (M1 vs M0) 5. # or % of patients with triple-negative breast cancer (TNBC): oestrogen & progesterone & HER2 receptors are 'negative' 6. Similarly, how many patients have oestrogen receptor positive tumours? 7. How many patients have HER2-positive tumours? 8. (similar questions for therapy)
C1126	As a patient looking at the IPS, I want to have the possibility to generate an IPS version with certain items removed, so that I can have different IPS versions to show to different health care providers.	major	AC1126.1	When displaying the IPS to the patient, AIDAVA provides the patient the possibility to create an additional customised version of the IPS - patient can specify which items shall be shown in that customised IPS version.
C1099	As a patient / curator / data user, I want to see the date to every medical parameter displayed in the IPS, so that the IPS is useful, as medical parameters make no sense without time information.	blocking	AC1099.1-p patient	When showing the IPS, AIDAVA displays a date to every medical parameter included in the IPS.
		major	AC1099.1-c curator	When showing the IPS, AIDAVA displays a date to every medical parameter included in the IPS.
		major	AC1099.1-u data user	AC0217.2 (<i>date when lab result/procedure/diagnosis has been done is displayed in the IPS</i>)
		blocking	AC1099.2-p patient	When showing the IPS to the patient in the MIDATA app, a date is shown to every medical parameter included in IPS.

Requirement ID	Requirement	Severity (for G2)	Acceptance Criterion ID	Acceptance Criterion
C1103	As a patient / curator / data user looking at the IPS displayed in AIDAVA, I want to see a well-formed rich IPS, so that I can easily read and understand the complete medical summary.	blocking	AC1103.1-p patient	The content of the IPS displayed by AIDAVA reflects the content of the source data ingested into AIDAVA. (i.e. all the important information, which is included in the source data, is also included in the IPS)
		major	AC1103.1-c curator	The content of the IPS displayed by AIDAVA reflects the content of the source data ingested into AIDAVA. (i.e. all the important information, which is included in the source data, shall be included in the IPS)
		major	AC1103.1-u data user	The content of the IPS displayed by AIDAVA reflects the content of the source data ingested into AIDAVA. (i.e. all the important information, which is included in the source data, shall be included in the IPS)
C1129	As a patient / curator / data user looking at the IPS displayed in AIDAVA/MIDATA, I want to see meaningful and human-understandable content (i.e. not codes but human-readable labels in my selected language are displayed), so that I can easily read and understand the complete medical summary.	blocking	AC1129.1-p patient	The content of the IPS is displayed in human-readable form (not codes) in the user's selected language.
		major	AC1129.1-c curator	The content of the IPS is displayed in human-readable form (not codes) in the user's selected language.
		major	AC1129.1-u data user	The content of the IPS is displayed in human-readable form (not codes) in the user's selected language.
C1145	As a patient, I want to get a text narrative of my IPS in lay language, so that I can easily understand my medical summary.	major	AC1145.1	AIDAVA shows the patient (on demand) a narrative summary of their IPS in lay language, with a mention that AIDAVA is a research prototype and the summary has not been validated and cannot be considered as usable for clinical decision making
C1146	As a data user (clinician) /patient looking at the curated data of a patient (e.g. IPS), I want to have (on demand) access to a "changes made by patient" log, so that I can be objective when caring for the patient.	major	AC1146.1	AIDAVA provides the clinician, who is assigned to the patient, (on demand) the possibility to see a "changes made by patient" log
		major	AC1146.1	AIDAVA provides the patient, (on demand) the possibility to see a "changes made by patient" log

Requirement ID	Requirement	Severity (for G2)	Acceptance Criterion ID	Acceptance Criterion
C1147	As a data user (clinician) / patient looking at the curated data of a patient, I want to see (on demand) a summary of the errors/inconsistencies that were removed from the patient's health data during data curation.	major	AC1147.1-u data user	AIDAVA provides the patient & clinician the possibility to see (on demand) a summary of the errors/inconsistencies that were removed from the patient's health data during data curation for the PHKG.
		major	AC1147.1-p patient	AIDAVA provides the patient & clinician the possibility to see (on demand) a summary of the errors/inconsistencies that were removed from the patient's health data during data curation for the PHKG
C1149		major	AC1149.1	The quality-of-life (QoL) questionnaire answers provided by the patient are included in the IPS (in the "Results"-section)

User Management

4 functional requirements concerning user management (user profile set up, access management, user account deletion) have been assessed in Phase 2 of Task 1.3 to be relevant for the AIDAVA prototype. For these 4 functional requirements in total 20 acceptance criteria have been defined.

Requirement ID	Requirement	Severity (for G2)	Acceptance Criterion ID	Acceptance Criterion
C0186 & C0189	As a user (data user/ curator / patient) using the AIDAVA system, I want to fill my user profile questionnaire in AIDAVA so that the AIDAVA health data curation and publishing virtual assistant is configured according to my profile	major	AC0186.1 (3)	The user profile of a PATIENT includes what happens with patient data in case of (a) death, (b) drop out (Note: per ICF patient accepts to keep the data during the project in case of dropout, so there are 2 possibilities: 1) donate the data (i.e. keep them - default) or 2) delete all data at end of project).
		minor	AC0186.2b	The user profile of a CURATOR includes additional information important for the system: user role, user name, email address, health literacy (and questionnaire answers), digital literacy (and questionnaire answers), name of related patients, preferred time for interaction; preferred approach on patient data (patient in bulk or separate)

Requirement ID	Requirement	Severity (for G2)	Acceptance Criterion ID	Acceptance Criterion
		major	AC0186.6b	When the patient confirms that the user profile is correct, the system generates the PHKG of the patient with identification information of the patient
		minor	AC0186.10	When the user is a PATIENT who updates information in their user profile, a message is automatically sent to the responsible research associate
C0189	As a patient/curator using the AIDAVA system, I want to fill my user profile questionnaire in AIDAVA so that the AIDAVA health data curation and publishing virtual assistant is configured according to my profile	minor	AC0189.3	The system considers the information of the user profile of the user (medical literacy, digital literacy, related curator) when asking help to the user through a HITL dialogue in the curation process
C0198	As a patient willing to delete my AIDAVA account, I expect the AIDAVA virtual assistant to make it clear (while I am using AIDAVA) that deleting my account is not reversible so that I can make an informed decision	minor	AC0198.3	Before deleting the data of the patient, the system informs the relevant expert curator and requests confirmation (this is for the prototype only during evaluation - NOT for the product)
		major	AC0198.5	The system informs the patient: <i>"Please note that you have created a personal MIDATA account and a personal Withings account during the project. You are free to keep these accounts as they belong to you. If you wish to delete data in those accounts or the accounts themselves, you need to go to the respective accounts."</i>
		major	AC0198.6-p patient	The system informs the patient of how to delete their account in AIDAVA
		minor	AC0198.6-c curator	When clicking on the user icon, the system also displays a "delete ACCOUNT" button (this is available any time)
		minor	AC0198.6-u data user	When clicking on the user icon, the system also displays a "delete ACCOUNT" button (this is available any time)
		minor	AC0198.7-p patient	The system points the user to the relevant point in the FAQs, where it is clearly described what happens when an account is deleted.
		minor	AC0198.7-c curator	The system points the user to the relevant point in the FAQs, where it is clearly described what happens when an account is deleted.

Requirement ID	Requirement	Severity (for G2)	Acceptance Criterion ID	Acceptance Criterion
		minor	AC0198.7-u data user	The system refers the user to the relevant point in the FAQs, where it is clearly described what happens when an account is deleted.
C0199 =C0162	As a patient willing to delete my AIDAVA account, I want to have the option to get a copy of all my data (in machine readable format) when I delete my account, so that I can use these data offline	minor	AC0199.1a	Before deleting the data of the patient, the system asks, if the patient requires to get their CURATED data in machine readable format - to be made available to them in PHKG format via secure means
		minor	AC0199.2	If the patient confirms that they want to receive their PHKG in machine readable format, the system extracts the PHKG of the patient (with a link to the AIDAVA ontology for documentation) and copy this in the secure file share accessible by the patient --> see AC0162.3
		minor	AC0199.3	When the User clicks on the delete, it is scheduled for deletion, during that time the patient can change their mind and prevent the deletion (48 hours), timer to show how much time left on the dashboard
		minor	AC0199.4	After 48 hours, the data available on the file share with a patient PHKG is deleted
		blocking	AC1066.3	AIDAVA updates the patient's user profile according to the patient's correction input and asks the patient to verify their updated user profile.
C1101	As a curator and as a data user setting up an AIDAVA account, I want my birthday and gender NOT to be mandatory fields for setting up an AIDAVA account (since that information is not important for my role in AIDAVA), so that I can setup an AIDAVA account without disclosing this information.	minor	AC1101.1a	Birthday and gender are not mandatory fields when setting up an AIDAVA expert curator account.
		minor	AC1101.1b	Birthday and gender are not mandatory fields when setting up an AIDAVA data user account.

Data Use

11 functional requirements concerning data use including provenance information and audit trail have been assessed in Phase 2 of Task 1.3 to be relevant for the AIDAVA prototype. For these 11 functional requirements in total 30 acceptance criteria have been defined.

Requirement ID	Requirement	Severity (for G2)	Acceptance Criterion ID	Acceptance Criterion
C0061	As a data user willing to check the data delivered from AIDAVA, I want the possibility to do a detailed check of any of the patient records included in the results delivered by the AIDAVA system, so that I can find out due to which parameters this record ended up in the result.	minor	AC0061.1	AC related to provenance (AUTHORIZED user) AC0070.2 AC0111.7 AC0111.8 AC0212.2 AC0212.3
C0210	As a retriever of medical information (patient, data user) considering to use AIDAVA, I want the provenance of the medical data documented (original sources, who entered or modified what, depending on the type of use case) so that I can know if data can be used.	blocking	AC0210.2	The system stores provenance information (- Source Information about where the data was obtained or collected from, and audit-trail with who, why, when) for each data element in the knowledge graph (SKHG and PHKG) – this is blocking, given the fundamental importance of provenance information in a well-curated medical health record)
		blocking	AC0210.2a	Provenance data must be available at the PHKG and published output level
		major	AC0210.2b	The provenance metadata should be stored in the PHKG in RDF format
		blocking	AC0210.2c	The provenance metadata related to the IPS should be included in the FHIR
		minor	AC0210.3	The system allows to download the log with provenance information of a specific data item within a spreadsheet for further analytics
C0216	As a data user (clinician) when considering to access medical data through AIDAVA, I want to have an overview of the different timepoints that the data were collected so that I can check the changes in patients' medical history over time	major	AC0216.1	The source data contains information about the time at which an event/finding/procedure happens

Requirement ID	Requirement	Severity (for G2)	Acceptance Criterion ID	Acceptance Criterion
C0212	As an expert curator using automatic data curation in AIDAVA, I want the application to open the referral letters, the digital history of the emergency card and the entries of the family doctor about the patient so that I can get the necessary additional information about the patient	major	AC0212.2	The authorized user has access to a list of data sources that have been included in the PHKG so far; each data source is displayed with a label and a metadata icon
		major	AC0212.3b	When the authorized user, clicks on the metadata icon of a data source, the system shows relevant FAIR metadata, including (b) in case of a procedure: instruments used (e.g. lab instrument, medical device type and number ...) (c) any modification
C0217	As a data user retrieving medical data from AIDAVA, I want information on the date when diagnoses/imaging/lab results have been created / done (note: this is usually different from when they have been entered into the AIDAVA health data curation and publishing virtual assistant!) so that I can track whether they are pre or post treatment.	major	AC0217.2	The date when a diagnosis/imaging/lab result have been done/created is displayed in the IPS
C0219	As a data user when making sure that the AIDAVA health data curation and publishing virtual assistant delivers the right data, I want to see who is the author of the document (uploaded when, changed it when) so I can verify the source of data and feel I can trust it	major	AC0219.1	see ACs related to display of provenance & computer traceability for outputs in scope of project (IPS, BC registry, SMART score): -> AC0225.3+4 (provenance of IPS & BC elements) --> C1085 (show provenance of values used by AIDAVA for calculating the SMART score) --> C1084 (show formula + values used for calculation of SMART score / BC registry metrics)
C0220	As a data user when making sure that the AIDAVA health data curation and publishing virtual assistant delivers the right data, I want to see the source of data so that I can adequately assess the information I see	major	AC0220.1	On demand, AIDAVA shows the source of curated data to the data user (clinician).

Requirement ID	Requirement	Severity (for G2)	Acceptance Criterion ID	Acceptance Criterion
C0221	As a data user when making sure that the AIDAVA health data curation and publishing virtual assistant delivers the right data, I want to see which institution the data originates from (medical facility or other, name of physician) So that I can assess the medical relevance/trustworthiness of data	major	AC0221.1	see ACs related to display of metadata / provenance & computer traceability for the 3 outputs in scope of the project (IPS, BC registry, SMART score): --> C0225: AC0225.3 (show provenance of IPS elements) + AC0225.4 (show provenance of BC elements) --> C1085 (SMART score: show provenance of the values used by AIDAVA for calculating the SMART score) --> C1084 (show formula + values used for calculation of SMART score / BC registry metrics)
C0222	As a data user when considering to access medical data through AIDAVA, I want to know what has been done in the previous stages and where the data in the AIDAVA health data curation and publishing virtual assistant is coming from (data from the hospital, data from other clinics or GP, or self-measured data from patients) in order to protect patient privacy.	major	AC0222.1	see ACs related to display of metadata / provenance & computer traceability for the 3 outputs in scope of the project (IPS, BC registry, SMART score): --> C0225: AC0225.3 (show provenance of IPS elements) + AC0225.4 (show provenance of BC elements) --> C1085 (SMART score: show provenance of the values used by AIDAVA for calculating the SMART score) --> C1084 (show formula + values used for calculation of SMART score / BC registry metrics)
		major	AC0222.2	Data source provenance information is easily accessible to the data user.
C0225 & C0289	As a patient / expert curator / data user (clinician) looking at the output of AIDAVA, I want that in the output (IPS, BC registry, SMART score) the AIDAVA system is providing (on demand) the data sources/document from where each of the data items in the output is coming from so that I can find out why the AIDAVA health data curation and publishing virtual assistant comes up with that specific curated information	major	AC0225.1-p patient	Each item in the PHKG includes provenance information (metadata + audit-trail on transformation steps): Provenance data must be available at the PHKG and published output level (=AC02102a)
		major	AC0225.1-c curator	Each item in the PHKG includes provenance information (metadata + audit-trail on transformation steps): Provenance data must be available at the PHKG and published output level (=AC02102a)
		major	AC0225.1-u data user	Each item in the PHKG includes provenance information (metadata + audit-trail on transformation steps): Provenance data must be available at the PHKG and published output level (=AC02102a)

Requirement ID	Requirement	Severity (for G2)	Acceptance Criterion ID	Acceptance Criterion
		major	AC0225.2-p patient	Each data item extracted from the PHKG (e.g. IPS) includes provenance information (metadata + audit trail on transformation steps)
		major	AC0225.2-c curator	Each data item extracted from the PHKG (e.g. IPS) includes provenance information (metadata + audit trail on transformation steps)
		major	AC0225.2-u data user	Each data item extracted from the PHKG (e.g. IPS, element to compute the SMART risks score, BC registry) includes provenance information (metadata + audit trail on transformation steps)
		major	AC0225.3-p patient	When viewing IPS, the patient can click on a data item and get the option to request "Where does this come from?" (provenance information); when clicking on this option the system displays the provenance information (source + metadata including provenance from data source + computer/curator traceability from the audit trail)) in a human readable form
		major	AC0225.3-c curator	When viewing IPS, the curator can click on a data item and get the option to request "Where does this come from?" (provenance information); when clicking on this option the system displays the provenance information (source + metadata including provenance from data source + computer/curator traceability from the audit trail)) in a human readable form
		major	AC0225.3-u data user	When viewing IPS, the data user (clinician) can click on a data item and get the option to request "Where does this come from?" (provenance information); when clicking on this option the system displays the provenance information (source + metadata including provenance from data source + computer/curator traceability from the audit trail)) in a human readable form

Requirement ID	Requirement	Severity (for G2)	Acceptance Criterion ID	Acceptance Criterion
		major	AC0225.4	When accessing the list of data elements included in the BC registry, the user can click on one of the data elements and get the option to request "provenance information"; when clicking on this option the system displays the provenance information in human readable form
C0213	As an expert curator / patient using automatic data curation in AIDAVA, I want to know what the changes to the KG were so that I have a better overview of the KG	minor	AC0213.1-c	The system shows on demand the changes done in the KG due to the user's curation work
		major	AC0213.1-p	The system shows the patient on demand the changes done in the IPS due to the patient's curation work
C1062	As a patient using AIDAVA I want AIDAVA to make sure that I can easily access my medical images.	major	AC1062.3	For G2. It is possible (for the patient) to have in AIDAVA access to the full resolution image and view it through a DICOM viewer (included in AIDAVA)
		major	AC1062.5	The possibility to include in the AIDAVA PHKG a unique identifier to a medical image is available.
C1082	As a patient, I want to see in my HDI app my answered QoL questionnaire, so that I can see what is in the QoL if I want to.	major	AC1082.1	The HDI app displays (on demand) the patient's answered QoL questionnaire in human readable format (not json...)

Quality Management

10 functional requirements concerning quality management have been assessed in Phase 2 of Task 1.3 to be relevant for the prototype to be implemented within the AIDAVA project. For these 10 functional requirements in total 36 acceptance criteria have been defined.

Requirement ID	Requirement	Severity (for G2)	Acceptance Criterion ID	Acceptance Criterion
C0215	As a patient and as a curator helping AIDAVA with manual data curation, I want to get information how confident the data XY is in the knowledge graph so that I can trust the AIDAVA health data curation and publishing virtual assistant	major	AC0215.1a-p patient	The system includes a data quality scoring/labelling - based on the content of the PHKG and the audit-trail to compute a data quality score/label at the level of a data item and at the level of the complete PHKG <i>(BEING DEVELOPED BY IDH in D4.6)</i>
		major	AC0215.1a-c curator	The system includes a data quality scoring/labelling - based on the content of the PHKG and the audit-trail to compute a data quality score/label at the level of a data item and at the level of the complete PHKG <i>(BEING DEVELOPED BY IDH in D4.6)</i>
		minor	AC0215.1b-p patient	For data items, which were retrieved/curated by AI tools, the KG stores confidence information provided by the respective AI tool as well as the source of this confidence information.
		major	AC0215.1b-c curator	For data items, which were retrieved/curated by AI tools, the KG stores confidence information provided by the respective AI tool as well as the source of this confidence information.
		minor	AC0215.2-p patient	For any data item (triple) included in the knowledge graph, the KG includes a score of quality - based on the data quality score system of AIDAVA - as well as the rationale for this score.
		minor	AC0215.2-c curator	For any data item (triple) included in the knowledge graph, the KG includes a score of quality - based on the data quality score system of AIDAVA - as well as the rationale for this score.

Requirement ID	Requirement	Severity (for G2)	Acceptance Criterion ID	Acceptance Criterion
		minor	AC0215.3-p patient	a) The system provides the patient the option to ask for the data quality score of a data item in the KG. (e.g. by clicking a "data quality information" button) b) On demand, the system displays the data quality score of a data item in the KG in human-readable form.
		minor	AC0215.3-c curator	a) The system provides the expert curator the option to ask for the data quality score of a data item in the KG. (e.g. by clicking a "data quality information" button) b) On demand, the system displays the data quality score of a data item in the KG in human-readable form.
		major	AC0215.4	a) When accessing the list of data elements included in the BC registry, the user can click on one of the data elements and gets the option to request the respective data quality score; b) when clicking on this option the system displays the respective data quality score in a human readable form
C1095	As a patient / curator, I want to have the possibility to change an answer (given some time ago), if I realise that there was a mistake in that answer, so that mistakes are corrected.	major	AC1095.1-p patient	a) AIDAVA provides the patient the possibility to re-visit a system's question, which they had answered some time ago, and change their answer to that system's question. b) AIDAVA updates the PHKG with the changed information provided by the patient. c) The change is included in the audit-trail.
		major	AC1095.1-c curator	a) AIDAVA provides the expert curator the possibility to re-visit a system's question, which they had answered some time ago, and change their answer to that system's question. b) AIDAVA updates the PHKG with the changed information provided by the expert curator. c) The change is included in the audit-trail.
C0292	As an expert curator using automatic data curation in AIDAVA, I want to change my response in case of an error / a mistake so that I can have support from the AIDAVA health data curation and publishing virtual assistant to guide with a more correct answer; the changes I made must be logged	major	AC0292.1	For G2: The system should allow the user to specify a data item, a date and a patient and retrieve that from the PHKG

Requirement ID	Requirement	Severity (for G2)	Acceptance Criterion ID	Acceptance Criterion
		major	AC0292.2	For G2. The system displays the retrieved information from the PHKG and allows the user to change this.
		major	AC0292.3	For G2. The PHKG is updated with the provided information and the change is included in the audit-trial
C0294	As a data user when considering to access medical data through AIDAVA, I want to know what kind of quality checks have been done so that I will have access to high quality data	major	AC0294.1a	AC0215.1 (<i>system provides data quality score at level of data item and PHKG...</i>)
		major	AC0294.1b	The system provides information about the quality checks performed on the accessed curated data.
C0290	As an expert curator willing to check the curated data in AIDAVA, I want to be able to do random checks on the curated data (e.g. check difference between source data and curated data) so that I can see if the AIDAVA health data curation and publishing virtual assistant has problems to curate certain kind of data or information	major	AC0290.3	For a curated source document, the system shows the curator (on demand) in human readable form the related curated data (SKG) which have been extracted from that source document. (Ideally, the source document and the curated data extracted from that source should be shown side-by-side).
C0298	As a patient using automatic data curation in AIDAVA, I want to check (on demand) what the AIDAVA health data curation and publishing virtual assistant has done when automatically curating data ... so that I can be sure that data curation is working correctly and the curated data are of high quality.	major	AC0298.3a	= AC0225.3-p (<i>show on demand provenance information for any data item displayed in the IPS</i>)
		major	AC0298.3b	For a curated source document, the system shows the patient (on demand) in human-readable form the related curated data (SKG) which have been extracted from that source document. (Ideally, the source document and the curated data extracted from that source should be shown side-by-side).
C0291	As an expert curator using automatic data curation in AIDAVA, I want the AIDAVA virtual assistant to check for when a report on a comparison between radiologic images is made in the ingested data and throw an alert if the compared images were not taken within a month from each other and are actually not comparable so that images that have been taken too far apart are not wrongly compared with each other	minor	AC0291.1	The system realizes if a radiology report includes a comparison of 2 images of a tumour in the context of breast cancer.

Requirement ID	Requirement	Severity (for G2)	Acceptance Criterion ID	Acceptance Criterion
		minor	AC0291.2	The system identifies if there is a period of more than 30 days between the 2 images compared.
		minor	AC0291.3	The system notifies the user that there was an issue comparing radiologic images (=more than 30 days between the dates of the images)
C1063	As a data user of the output of AIDAVA I want to have a clear understanding on the type of professional who entered information in the medical record	major	AC1063.2	The system includes a repository (master data DB) with information on the staff entering information in the medical record; this repository must include the designation (Mr, Mss, Dr, Prof..), profession and speciality of the person.
C1068	As a patient / data user I want AIDAVA to show me how good the quality of my / the patient's curated data is, so that I can understand the quality of the data.	minor	AC1068.1	= AC0215.1 (...system includes a data quality scoring...at the level of data items in the KG and at the level of the PHKG)
		major	AC1068.2-p patient	AIDAVA displays a meaningful data quality score for the patient's curated data (at PHKG level) to the patient.
		major	AC1068.2-u data user	AIDAVA displays a meaningful data quality score for a patient's curated data (at PHKG level) to the clinician.
C1143	As a patient / expert curator / data user (clinician) looking at the IPS displayed by AIDAVA, when I spot that there is a mistake in the curated data, I want to mark the respective element in the curated data as "erroneous" so that it is not further used by AIDAVA (i.e. not published and not used for calculations within AIDAVA)	blocking	AC1143.1-p patient	When AIDAVA displays the IPS to a patient, the patient is provided with the possibility to mark any element of the IPS as "erroneous".
		major	AC1143.1-c curator	When AIDAVA displays the IPS to an expert curator, the expert curator is provided with the possibility to mark any element of the IPS as "erroneous".
		major	AC1143.1-u data user	When AIDAVA displays the IPS to a data user (clinician), the clinician is provided with the possibility to mark any element of the IPS as "erroneous".
		major	AC1143.2-p patient	When an element of the IPS is marked by a patient/expert curator/clinician as "erroneous", the respective element in the curated data is automatically flagged as "erroneous". This is logged in the audit-trail.

Requirement ID	Requirement	Severity (for G2)	Acceptance Criterion ID	Acceptance Criterion
		major	AC1143.2-c curator	When an element of the IPS is marked by a patient/expert curator/clinician as "erroneous", the respective element in the curated data is automatically flagged as "erroneous". This is logged in the audit-trail.
		major	AC1143.2-u data user	When an element of the IPS is marked by a patient/expert curator/clinician as "erroneous", the respective element in the curated data is automatically flagged as "erroneous". This is logged in the audit-trail.
C1144	As a patient / expert curator looking at the curation results of a document (SKG) displayed by AIDAVA, when I spot that there is a mistake in the curated data, I want to mark the respective element in the curated data as "erroneous" so that it is not further used by AIDAVA (i.e. not published & not used for calculations within AIDAVA)	major	AC1144.1-p patient	When AIDAVA displays the SKG of a curated document in human readable form to a patient, the patient is provided with the possibility to mark any element of the SKG as "erroneous".
		major	AC1144.1-c curator	When AIDAVA displays the SKG of a curated document (in human readable form) to an expert curator, the expert curator is provided with the possibility to mark any element of the SKG as "erroneous".
		major	AC1144.2-p patient	When an element of the displayed SKG is marked by a patient/expert curator as "erroneous", the respective element in the curated data is automatically flagged as "erroneous". This is logged in the audit-trail.
		major	AC1144.2-c curator	When an element of the displayed SKG is marked by a patient/expert curator as "erroneous", the respective element in the curated data is automatically flagged as "erroneous". This is logged in the audit-trail.

3.3.2 Non-functional Requirements

Non-functional requirements define the overall qualities that the AIDAVA health data curation and publishing virtual assistant must possess in order to meet performance-related goals and objectives, such as speed, throughput, capacity, and other performance-related factors.

In total 14 non-functional requirements have been assessed in Phase 2 of Task 1.3 to be relevant for the AIDAVA prototype. For these 14 requirements, 17 acceptance criteria have been formulated. In the following paragraphs, these requirements and related acceptance criteria are listed per category.

Serviceability / Helpdesk

Refers to the ease with which a system or application can be serviced or repaired in the event of a failure or malfunction. This is important because they ensure that the system can be quickly and easily repaired or serviced, which can reduce downtime and minimise the impact of failures or malfunctions.

3 requirements related to this category have been assessed in Phase 2 of Task 1.3 to be relevant for the AIDAVA prototype.

Requirement ID	Requirement	Severity (for G2)	Acceptance Criterion ID	Acceptance Criterion
C0201	As an expert curator helping AIDAVA with manual data curation, I want to have the option to ask the support staff of AIDAVA if I do not understand the question of the AIDAVA health data curation and publishing virtual assistant so that feedback is provided to improve the AIDAVA health data curation and publishing virtual assistant	major	AC0201.2	AIDAVA provides the curator with the possibility to directly reference the question/page they have trouble with
C0202	As a data user willing to check the data delivered from AIDAVA, I want to have the possibility to report errors in the curated data, so that incorrect information in the AIDAVA health data curation and publishing virtual assistant can be corrected.	major	AC0202.1	AIDAVA provides a feature to report errors found in the curated data
C1023	Extent to which the system is documented for service and maintenance purposes. Example: System should have clear and detailed documentation for service and maintenance purposes.	major	AC1023.1	see AC1018.1 (<i>put together a document with the different sources of documentation - including deliverables and GITHUB as the basis documentation of AIDAVA</i>)

Maintainability

This category describes the ease with which a system or application can be maintained and updated over its lifetime, i.e. ability to be modified, updated, or repaired without affecting its overall functionality or performance. This is important because requirements of this category ensure that the system can be easily maintained and updated, which can reduce the cost and time associated with system maintenance and updates.

3 requirements related to this category have been assessed in Phase 2 of Task 1.3 to be relevant for the AIDAVA prototype.

Requirement ID	Requirement	Severity (for G2)	Acceptance Criterion ID	Acceptance Criterion
C1018	Extent to which the system is documented, including the code, user manuals, and technical documentation. Example: The system should have clear and detailed documentation that can be easily understood and updated by future developers or maintainers	minor	AC1018.1	A document listing the different sources of documentation should be available - including deliverables and GITHUB as the basis documentation of AIDAVA
C1019	Extent to which the system can be tested and validated to ensure that it continues to function correctly after updates or modifications. Examples: Unit testing, Integration testing, Performance testing; Automated test cases that can be run after updates or modifications; Availability of testing data sets and testing scenarios. - Test coverage percentage (e.g. unit testing / code coverage = 80% in a hospital system)	major	AC1019.1	1. the overall AIDAVA backbone should have automatically executed module test, integration test and regression test 2. Each component should have integration & testing specification
C1022	The following components must have strict version / release management a) Centrally (and synchronised with the site instances): - the library of curation tools, - the Reference Ontology b) In each site where AIDAVA is deployed: - the User Directory, - the Catalogue of Data Sources, - the Master Data repository	major	AC1022.2	There is version control for the Ontology

Usability

This category relates to a system's ability to be easy to use and intuitive for its intended users, i.e. to provide an effective and efficient user experience, and to be easy to learn and use. This is important because it ensures that the system is user-friendly and meets the needs and expectations of its intended users. 4 requirements related to this category have been assessed in Phase 2 of Task 1.3 to be relevant for the AIDAVA prototype.

Requirement ID	Requirement	Severity (for G2)	Acceptance Criterion ID	Acceptance Criterion
C1042	The system is easy to use and navigate for the patients and the expert curators, i.e. for its intended users. Note: this does not apply to the AIDAVA admin and Site Admin	major	AC1042.2	curation workflows are easy to use and navigate for the patients and expert curators (to be measured through system usability scale during evaluation)
C1043	The system is easy to learn and use for its intended users, measured by filling the System Usability Scale questionnaire used for assessing the prototype (first primary end point in the study protocol) #1. Maximise acceptance by end users and potential involvement of citizens in curating health data)	major	AC1043.1	System Usability Scale (SUS) score should be above 75
C1044	System is efficient and effective in performing its intended tasks; this is measured by checking the following primary endpoints in the study protocol #2. Measure impact on workload for quality enhancement of data #3. Measure quality of data resulting from the data curation and publishing - in terms of their interoperability and reusability #4. Assess percentage of reuse of content of clinical narratives	major	AC1044.1	#2. impact on workload: time for curation of a source document should be less than 5 min on average (for patient and curator)
		major	AC1044.2	#3. quality of data at individual level should have a high score across all dimension
		major	AC1044.3	#4. % of reuse (within the annotation domain) should be above 90%
C1047	Possibility to have a copy of entity records in both human readable and electronic form, where the meaning has been preserved (CFR2)	minor	AC1047,1	only for IPS - not for the full PHKG (only through GraphDB UI)

General Design

4 requirements related to this category have been assessed in Phase 2 of Task 1.3 to be relevant for the AIDAVA prototype.

Requirement ID	Requirement	Severity (for G2)	Acceptance Criterion ID	Acceptance Criterion
C1052	Regular release of the product with release notes Note: In the context of AIDAVA there will be at least 2 releases: G1 and G2	minor	AC1052.1	a) release of G1 with release notes b) release of G2 with release notes
C1064	As a research associate assessing AIDAVA/evaluating results/filling in questionnaires, I want AIDAVA to provide the number of data that were transformed/curated automatically by the system, the number of data that required human intervention and among these the number of questions that were successfully answered.	major	AC1064.1	These figures will be either provided to the research associate that will fill the RedCap form or automatically entered in the RedCap form
C1057	Ensure that output (i.e. curated) data is of high quality i.e. there is a correct transformation from the original data. In case 100% certainty cannot be ensured during transformation, provide a quality score. This will be measured following primary end point #3 of the study protocol Measure quality of data resulting from the data curation and publishing - in terms of their interoperability and reusability	major	AC1057.1	= AC1044.2
C1058	Publish results on ZENODO (EOSC) or on GitHub, using appropriate licence & security - User requirements (D1.2 and D1.3) - User stories with performance criteria - Executable code	major	AC1058.1	publish G1 results
		minor	AC1058.2	publish G2 results as part of KER3 and store into a secure data store (AIDAVA GITHUB ?)
C1064	As a research associate assessing AIDAVA/evaluating results/filling in questionnaires, I want AIDAVA to provide the number of data that were transformed/curated automatically by the system, the number of data that required human intervention and among these the number of questions that were successfully answered.	major	AC1064.1	These figures will be either provided to the research associate that will fill the RedCap form or automatically entered in the RedCap form

3.3.3 Requirements related to Training & Documentation

46 requirements related to training and documentation have been assessed to be relevant for the AIDAVA prototype. For these 46 requirements, 48 acceptance criteria have been formulated.

Requirement ID	Requirement	Severity (for G2)	Acceptance Criterion ID	Acceptance Criterion
C0200	As a patient willing to delete my AIDAVA account, I want to have the option to delete all my data so that no-one can use this data anymore from this point forward	blocking	AC0200.2	In G2: It is clearly explained to the participating patients (in the SIP and ICF) when and how they can delete their AIDAVA account and their data in AIDAVA. --> see AC0274.1 (<i>information in the FAQs regarding how patient can delete their data...</i>) --> see AC0273.1 (<i>information in the FAQs regarding account deletion...</i>)
C0253	As a data user willing to check the data delivered from AIDAVA, I expect (the manufacturer of) AIDAVA to tell/confirm that the AIDAVA health data curation and publishing virtual assistant works reliably, so that it is not my duty to check whether the results are correct	major	AC0253.1b	The FAQs + SIP include information regarding the (non) reliable functioning of AIDAVA
C0249	As an expert curator ingesting medical data into AIDAVA, I want to know if there are specific validation steps for catching errors i.e. if there are specific points from the data entry that are routinely checked by the AIDAVA health data curation and publishing virtual assistant (for instance, if there is an automatic tool to catch time-related errors in the data entry), so that I know if errors are automatically caught	minor	AC0249.1	The system provides the option to read the documentation of the system, which includes the rules of how it catches errors (SHACL rules)
		major	AC0249.2	The FAQs include how the system automatically catches errors (SHACL rules)
C0251	As an expert curator using the AIDAVA system, I want to know what the AIDAVA system is capable of and what I can expect from AIDAVA so that I can know what I can expect from AIDAVA	major	AC0251.1	Information about what the AIDAVA app is capable of and what can be expected from the AIDAVA app is included in the documentation and in the FAQs.
C0252	As an expert curator using the AIDAVA system, I want to know what I need to do so that I know how to use the AIDAVA health data curation and publishing virtual assistant	major	AC0252.1	A step-by-step guide for AIDAVA expert curators is included in the manual and in the FAQs.

Requirement ID	Requirement	Severity (for G2)	Acceptance Criterion ID	Acceptance Criterion
C0255	As a data user when considering to access medical data through AIDAVA, I want to know if AIDAVA includes pseudonymised data so that the data are compliant with the data privacy protocols	minor	AC0255.1	This information is included in the manual and in the FAQs.
C0256	As a data user willing to check the data delivered from AIDAVA, I want to have access to proper documentation to understand for example the assumptions of the AIDAVA health data curation and publishing virtual assistant so that I have a basic understanding of the dataset nature I have access to	minor	AC0256.1	This information is included in the manual and in the FAQs.
C0257	As a data user willing to check the data delivered from AIDAVA, I want to have access to the documentation used for the data curation process and the data provenance so that I understand the process that has been done before my access to the data (validation process beforehand)	minor	AC0257.1	This information is included in the manual and in the FAQs.
C0258	As a data user when considering to access medical data through AIDAVA, I want to know what kind of technical knowledge I need to have so that I will be able to access the AIDAVA tool and the data included on it	minor	AC0258.1	This information is included in the manual and in the FAQs.
C0259	As a data user when considering to access medical data through AIDAVA, I want to have information regarding the data curation process so that I have an idea if I can trust the data that I will have access to	minor	AC0259.1	This information is included in the manual and in the FAQs.
C1111	As a patient contemplating/starting to use AIDAVA, I want to get information regarding the objective and intended use of the AIDAVA app, so that I can understand how/what for I can use AIDAVA.	blocking	AC1111.1	Information regarding the objective and intended use of the AIDAVA app is available in the FAQs and also accessible from the first screen of the app before login to AIDAVA
C0261	As a patient contemplating registering to AIDAVA, I want to know beforehand what the AIDAVA system is capable of and what I can expect from AIDAVA so that I can assess the benefits of using AIDAVA	major	AC0261.1	= AC0251.1 (<i>Information about what the AIDAVA app is capable of and what can be expected from the AIDAVA app is included in the documentation and in the FAQs.</i>)
C0262	As a patient contemplating registering to AIDAVA, I want to know beforehand what AIDAVA is doing with my data and where my data uploaded to AIDAVA will be stored so that I can trust the AIDAVA health data curation and publishing virtual assistant	major	AC0262.1	Information regarding what AIDAVA is doing with a patient's data and where data uploaded to AIDAVA is stored, is available in the FAQs and also accessible from the first screen of the app before login to AIDAVA

Requirement ID	Requirement	Severity (for G2)	Acceptance Criterion ID	Acceptance Criterion
C0263	As a patient contemplating registering to AIDAVA, I want to know beforehand who will be able to access/see/use my data uploaded to AIDAVA so that I can trust the AIDAVA health data curation and publishing virtual assistant	major	AC0263.1	Information regarding who will be/is able to access a patient's data uploaded to AIDAVA, is available in the FAQs and also accessible from the first screen of the app before login to AIDAVA
C0264	As a patient contemplating registering to AIDAVA, I want to know beforehand how I can control who gets to see which part of my data in AIDAVA so that I can decide to use the AIDAVA health data curation and publishing virtual assistant	major	AC0264.1	Information regarding how a patient can control who gets to see which part of their data uploaded to AIDAVA, is available in the FAQs and also accessible from the first screen of the app before login to AIDAVA
C0266	As a patient contemplating registering to AIDAVA, I want to know beforehand whether there is going to be a cost and if so who is paying for using AIDAVA so that I can trust and decide whether to use the AIDAVA health data curation and publishing virtual assistant	major	AC0266.1	Information regarding any costs and financing of AIDAVA is available in the FAQs and also accessible from the first screen of the app before login to AIDAVA.
C0267	As a patient contemplating registering to AIDAVA, I want to know beforehand about the data ownership so that I can trust the AIDAVA health data curation and publishing virtual assistant	major	AC0267.1	Information regarding the data ownership in AIDAVA is included in the FAQs and also accessible from the first screen of the app before login to AIDAVA.
C0268	As a patient contemplating registering to AIDAVA, I want to know beforehand what I will need to do when using the AIDAVA virtual assistant and how I can use the AIDAVA health data curation and publishing virtual assistant so that I can assess how easy it is to use	major	AC0268.1	Information regarding what a patient needs to do when using AIDAVA is included in the FAQs and also accessible from the first screen of the app before login to AIDAVA.
C0269	As a patient contemplating registering to AIDAVA, I want to be informed about the measures in place to ensure reliability and security of the AIDAVA health data curation and publishing virtual assistant so that I can trust the AIDAVA health data curation and publishing virtual assistant	major	AC0269.1	Information regarding the measures in place to ensure reliability and security of the AIDAVA app is included in the FAQs and also accessible from the first screen of the app before login to AIDAVA.

Requirement ID	Requirement	Severity (for G2)	Acceptance Criterion ID	Acceptance Criterion
C1112	As a patient contemplating/starting to use AIDAVA, I want to get information regarding the security of my data (Where are my data stored? Who has got access to my data? What security measures are in place to prevent abuse/leakage of my data? What if I want to stop using AIDAVA?), so that I can trust AIDAVA.	major	AC1112.1	This information is available in the FAQs, and accessible before login from the first screen of the patient's app. --> AC0262.1 (<i>where are data uploaded to AIDAVA stored...</i>) --> AC0269.1 (<i>measures in place to ensure reliability and security of AIDAVA...</i>) --> AC0263.1 (<i>who has access to the data uploaded to AIDAVA...</i>) --> AC0264.1 (<i>how can a patient control who gets access to their data in AIDAVA...</i>) --> AC0273.1 (<i>how can I delete my account...</i>)
C0270	As a patient contemplating registering to AIDAVA, I want to be informed about the role of the expert curator, who they are and what they do, and how they will interact with my personal health data so that I can decide to use the AIDAVA health data curation and publishing virtual assistant	major	AC0270.1	Information about the role of the expert curator is available in the FAQs, and accessible before login from the first screen of the patient's app
C0271	As a patient contemplating registering to AIDAVA, I want to know how (for what purpose) my data in AIDAVA will be used so that I can trust the AIDAVA health data curation and publishing virtual assistant	major	AC0271.1	Information regarding for what purpose data uploaded to AIDAVA are used is available in the FAQs and accessible before login from the first screen of the patient's app.
C0272	As a patient contemplating registering to AIDAVA, I want to know beforehand what happens to my data when I delete my account or do not want to use the AIDAVA health data curation and publishing virtual assistant anymore so that I can decide to use the AIDAVA health data curation and publishing virtual assistant	major	AC0272.1	Information regarding what happened to a patient's data upon account deletion is available in the FAQs and accessible before login from the first screen of the patient's app.
C0273	As a patient contemplating registering to AIDAVA, I want to know beforehand, how I can delete my AIDAVA account so that I am sure I can quit using AIDAVA whenever I want	major	AC0273.1	Information regarding account deletion is available in the FAQs and accessible before login from the first screen of the patient's app.
C0274	As a patient contemplating registering to AIDAVA, I want to know beforehand, how I can delete my data from the AIDAVA health data curation and publishing virtual assistant so that I am sure I can quit using AIDAVA whenever I want	major	AC0274.1	Information regarding how a patient can delete their data from AIDAVA is available in the FAQs and accessible before login from the first screen of the patient's app.

Requirement ID	Requirement	Severity (for G2)	Acceptance Criterion ID	Acceptance Criterion
C0275	As a patient contemplating registering to AIDAVA, I want to know beforehand how I can retrieve my data i.e. get my data back from the AIDAVA health data curation and publishing virtual assistant so that I can decide to use the AIDAVA health data curation and publishing virtual assistant	major	AC0275.1	Information regarding how a patient can retrieve their curated data from AIDAVA is available in the FAQs and accessible before login from the first screen of the patient's app.
C0276	As a patient willing to delete my AIDAVA account, I want the AIDAVA health data curation and publishing virtual assistant to clearly communicate to me what will happen to my data if I delete my account so that I can understand how my data is affected when I delete my account.	major	AC0276.1	--> AC0273.1 (<i>information regarding account deletion...</i>)
C0277	As a patient using the AIDAVA system, I want to have an OFFLINE guide on how to use the AIDAVA health data curation and publishing virtual assistant so that I can check the guide if needed and learn how to use the AIDAVA health data curation and publishing virtual assistant;	major	AC0277.1	--> AC1117.1 (<i>easy to follow step-by-step guide for patients is available for patients offline...</i>)
C1117	As a patient using the AIDAVA system, I want to get an easy to use manual in "cookbook-style" (rather than a complicated ppt), so that it is easy for me to find out what I need to do if I cannot remember.	major	AC1117.1	An easy to follow step-by-step ("cookbook-style") guide for patients on how to use AIDAVA is available in plain language offline (i.e. in printed format)
C1141	As a patient using AIDAVA, I want that the AIDAVA training is adjusted to my skills and technical background, so that I can easily follow the training.	major	AC1141.1	Training materials provided by AIDAVA to the patients are suitable for people with low level of digital literacy.
C0250	As a site architect ingesting medical data into AIDAVA, I want to know if there is an option to create imaging metadata around the data that will be uploaded so that I can understand better the data	minor	AC0250.1	Imaging Metadata should be included in the DICOM file which should be processed as a data source
C0254	As a data user when considering to access medical data through AIDAVA, I want to know if there is a possibility to access data in batch processing so that I know whether I can have access to many patients directly	minor	AC0254.1	This information is included in the documentation
C0260	As a data user when considering to access medical data through AIDAVA, I want a detailed guide to the AIDAVA system with an explanation of the interface and the catalogue so that I can quickly start to use AIDAVA and find my way around.	minor	AC0260.1	This information is included in the documentation

Requirement ID	Requirement	Severity (for G2)	Acceptance Criterion ID	Acceptance Criterion
C0278	As a patient using the AIDAVA system, I want to have an ONLINE guide on how to use the AIDAVA health data curation and publishing virtual assistant so that I can check the guide if needed and learn how to use the AIDAVA health data curation and publishing virtual assistant	minor	AC0278.1	This information is included as an easy-to-follow step-by-step guide (in "cookbook-style") in the FAQs.
C0279	As a 3rd-party app developer considering to use AIDAVA, I want to know how many data are expected (volume, data types)	minor	AC0279.1	This information is included in the documentation
C0280	As a 3rd-party app developer considering to use AIDAVA, I want to know how often new data will be available	minor	AC0280.1	This information is included in the documentation
C0281	As a 3rd-party app developer considering to use AIDAVA, I want to know how up to date must the data be in the app	minor	AC0281.1	This information is included in the documentation
C0344	As a 3rd-party app developer considering to use AIDAVA, I want to know where my information will be used and send to by AIDAVA, so that privacy of the patient is respected.	major	AC0344.1	This information is included in the documentation
C0357	As a patient and as a 3rd-party app developer considering to use AIDAVA, I want to know the exact governance rules of the data entered	major	AC0357.1-p patient	The exact governance rules of the data entered into AIDAVA are clearly described (in plain language) in the information material for patients. --> AC0262.1 (where are data uploaded to AIDAVA stored...) --> AC0263.1 (who has access to the data uploaded to AIDAVA...) --> AC0264.1 (how can a patient control who gets access to their data in AIDAVA...) --> AC0267.1 (data ownership) --> AC0271.1 (for what purpose are data uploaded to AIDAVA used...)
		minor	AC0357.1-d data user	The exact governance rules of the data entered into AIDAVA are available in the documentation, which is accessible to (interested) 3rd parties.
C0358	As a 3rd-party app developer retrieving medical data from AIDAVA for my app, I want clear documentation of the standards used by AIDAVA so that a high quality on my side is maintained	minor	AC0358.1	The standards used are documented.
C0364	As a 3rd-party app developer retrieving medical data from AIDAVA for my app, I want to know how the data are linked together	minor	AC0364	This information is included in the documentation.

Requirement ID	Requirement	Severity (for G2)	Acceptance Criterion ID	Acceptance Criterion
C0371	As a patient considering to use AIDAVA, I want to know the end goal that my data is being used for so that I can give the mandatory informed consent to get the right to collect data (That cannot be carte blanche upfront)	major	AC0371.1	This information is included in the SIP.
C0382	As a patient using the AIDAVA system, I want to know how my data (from Health Data Intermediary (e.g. MIDATA) are used by AIDAVA --> see C1135	major	AC0382.1	= AC1135.1 (<i>clear explanation of relationship and dataflows between AIDAVA and MIDATA...</i>)
C1135	As a patient contemplating/starting to use AIDAVA, I want to receive clear and explicit information / explanations regarding the relationship between the used environments/applications (AIDAVA, MIDATA, Withings...) including the directions of data flow, so that I can understand these beforehand and take an informed decision regarding my usage of AIDAVA.	major	AC1135.1	These topics are explicitly and clearly explained in plain language in the SIP and guide for patients.
C0387	As a system user using the AIDAVA system, I want to know how human interaction is integrated - Will the AIDAVA health data curation and publishing virtual assistant say: "Come back later, your data is not yet ready"?	minor	AC0387.1	In the AIDAVA prototype assessment study, this is included in the training.
C1069	As a patient, with no familiarities with medical and computer terms, I want to have access to a glossary, so that I can more easily understand	major	AC1069.1	A glossary is included in the FAQs (ONLINE) !!
C1113	As a patient using AIDAVA, I want to get information about what I can do with my IPS (Can I download? Can I show it to doctors? Is it available in other languages?), so that I know how I can use my IPS.	major	AC1113.1	This information is available in the FAQs and in the SIP.

Material for Training & Documentation

As already described in deliverable D1.3, to fulfil the different requirements related to training and documentation, the following 4 documents were defined in Phase 1 of Task 1.3:

- 1) System Manual – a guideline for installation, configuration and maintenance of AIDAVA addressed to site administrators and developers
- 2) User Manual – a guideline (as part of the training material) explaining the usage of AIDAVA to patients, expert curators, and data users (e.g. clinicians)
- 3) FAQ (Frequently Asked Questions) – online information explaining important aspects of AIDAVA to patients, expert curators, data users and site administrators
- 4) Product Manual - Information on the product "to be" that can be used as a basis for potential customers - like third party app developers - of this future product to assess the benefit and value

In the following paragraphs, an outline of the envisaged content of these 4 documents is provided.

System Manual

Objective: Guideline for Installation, Configuration, Maintenance

Target Audience: Site Administrators, Developers

Expected Content

Installation - prerequisites

- Licensing
- System architecture and interfaces
- System requirements
 - software and hardware (docker, VMware?)
 - storage (DB type, size) -
 - CPU/GPU
- Data Sources metadata
- Imaging metadata management
- Instructions for set-up/installation and data ingestion
- How to upload and download data in / from AIDAVA using the API (incl. Data Transfer Specification): API (endpoint / formats / version / semantics) for retrieving/test medical data

Configuration - How to perform curation tool onboarding

Not applicable - done centrally before the tool is deployed in each site

Configuration - How to perform data sources onboarding

How to enter information into Data Source catalogue

Configuration - How to manage users

- Description of roles and access rights of each role: who has access to which data,
- How to manage user information into the User Directory (how to enter; how to adapt information such as role, PWD, personal info...)

Support

- Contact person
- How to restore solution in case of problem
- Support process (who is responsible of support for the system including contact name)

Maintenance

- What does it include - how often - what is needed?
- What interfaces need to be updated
- What access do I need for maintenance

User Manual

Objective: Information for the users (as part of the training)

Target Audience: all potential users (patients, curators, data users)

Expected Content

<p>General information</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Goals of the AIDAVA health data curation and publishing virtual assistant and main functionalities ● Purpose of the usage of health data in AIDAVA in a detailed way ● How the tool is supposed to interact with the local hospital information system and subsystems ● Define tasks expected from patients and for expert curators, and level of literacy needed ● Standards supported (for ingestion and publishing) <p>Ensure system can be trusted</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Legal foundation on which AIDAVA is based ● How does AIDAVA comply with data protection regulation and is secure; <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ are data pseudonymized; ○ what happens to my data when deleting my account; ● How AIDAVA protects the data that have been ingested ● How data are curated and how does AIDAVA ensure that curated data are of quality ● Confirm that AIDAVA is not a medical product ● Confirm that AIDAVA does not make diagnoses ● How data in the AIDAVA app (smartphone of a patient) is accessible <p>Support</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Clear definition of responsibilities for AIDAVA ● How often there will be updates and security patches ● Need to know if back-ups are necessary and if yes, how ● How to report bugs/issues
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FAQ

Objective: Provide information to users on critical aspects of the systems

Target Audience: all potential users (patients, curators, data users) as well as site administrators

Expected Content

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● How data protection is ensured - are data pseudonymized; is it possible to delete my data ● What about security ● Which error can be identified and how? ● Main functionalities of AIDAVA ● How to use the system ● Certification by manufacturer ● Access to online help/documentation ● How to report bugs and issues to improve the system
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Product Manual

Objective: Information on the product "to be" that can be used as a basis for potential customers - like third party app developers - of this future product to assess the benefit and value

Target Audience: developers/potential customers, site administrators, patients and other users with advanced knowledge and interest in the product

Expected Content

- **Benefits** of using AIDAVA and curated data
- **Standards in use:**
 - supported formats & version for data ingestion, storage and data use
 - licensing of used standards
 - quality standards supported (e.g. ISO 27001)
 - compliance with guidelines Medical Device Regulations (MDR) and AI
- **Data privacy aspects**
 - liability,
 - data linkage,
 - consent management
- **Data ingestion:** batch or on demand - based on Create, Read, Update, Delete (CRUD)
- **Data use**
 - Standard ways to display and retrieve data
 - Allowed purpose of data use
 - Expected quality of data
- **Storage**
 - Size restrictions
 - Type of data store, cloud or local
 - Permanent data storage or other – for ingested data and for PHKG
- **Pricing & business model**

3.4 Regulatory requirements

Regulatory requirements are related to a system's ability to comply with applicable laws, regulations, standards, and guidelines related to its operation and use. This is important because it ensures that the system operates within the boundaries set by regulatory authorities, and avoids legal or regulatory penalties or other adverse consequences.

In WP4 of the AIDAVA project, the regulatory framework conditions for an 'AI-powered virtual assistant for health data curation and publishing' have been analysed⁷. Thereby regulatory requirements for a future "AIDAVA-like" product have been identified evolving from to the EU AI Act, which came into force on 1st of August 2024.

Note: Since the EU AI Act will only be effective from 2nd of August 2026, which is after the development and testing of the AIDAVA G2 prototype, all regulatory requirements listed in the following table are deemed to be out of scope for the prototype but clearly in scope of a future product.

In the following table, for each acceptance criterion also the responsible party is listed, this is the organisation or entity responsible for meeting that specific requirement according to the EU AI Act. Thereby the following roles, as specified by the EU AI Act, are relevant for AIDAVA:

- Provider: as per the AI Act "...means a natural or legal person, public authority, agency or other body that develops an AI system or a general-purpose AI model or that has an AI system or a general-purpose AI model developed and places it on the market or puts the AI system into service under its own name or trademark, whether for payment or free of charge..."
- Deployer: as per the AI Act "...means a natural or legal person, public authority, agency or other body using an AI system under its authority except where the AI system is used in the course of a personal non-professional activity..."
- Data Source: Entity providing training and / or validation data

⁷ The results of that work in WP4 are described in detail in deliverable D4.8.

ID	Regulatory Requirement	Applicability (component of AIDAVA)	Responsible Party	Acceptance Criteria	Priority
AIDRec001	The AIDAVA tool should allow users to flag any areas of uncertainty in terms of AI recommendations.	Frontend	Provider	For consideration after G2 Evaluation	MINOR
AIDRec002	The AIDAVA tool should allow users to report any unintended outcomes based on the AI Tool.	Frontend	Provider	For consideration after G2 Evaluation	MINOR
AIDRec003	The AIDAVA tool could offer the option to turn off any AI components	Frontend	Provider	For consideration after G2 Evaluation	MINOR
AIDRec004	The AIDAVA tool could offer the option to turn off any AI components in terms of recommendations.	Frontend	Provider	For consideration after G2 Evaluation	MINOR
AIDRec005	The AIDAVA tool could show the points of intervention that the AI Tool has made as a log or report in terms of transparency.	Frontend	Provider	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. A Clear representation of AI component activity 2. Include a timestamp of the component's activity, what process encapsulated the activity and what data items and outputs were affected 3. Present it in a human-readable format <p>N.B. The strict requirement is for the logs to be available and evidence to be submitted as per AIDRec001 - 004. The requirement here is for maximum transparency</p>	MINOR
AIDRec006	The AIDAVA tool could show the points of intervention that the AI Tool has made as a log or report in terms of user agency.	Frontend	Provider	As AIDRec005 but for the purpose of Human Agency	MINOR
AIDRec007	The AIDAVA tool could show the points of intervention that the AI Tool has made as a log or report in terms of operational oversight.	Frontend	Provider	As AIDRec005 but for the purpose of Human Oversight	MINOR

ID	Regulatory Requirement	Applicability (component of AIDAVA)	Responsible Party	Acceptance Criteria	Priority
AIDRec008	Infrastructure that is running the AIDAVA platform should be certified for cybersecurity (e.g. the certification scheme created by the Cybersecurity Act in Europe) or demonstrate compliance with specific security standards.	Infrastructure	Provider, Deployer	1. To demonstrate certification by providing a certification issued by certification authorities (e.g. ISO authority certificate). OR 2. To demonstrate adherence to standards without certification (including details of security policies, data protection policies, user administration policies, breach reporting policies, regular meetings of infrastructure providers / ICT, Service Level Agreements, antivirus software management and regular software patches and updates) N.B. This should include details for AIDRec009 - AIDRec0013 as outlined.	MAJOR
AIDRec009	Any training and development of the algorithms or model generation should be certified for cybersecurity (e.g. the certification scheme created by the Cybersecurity Act in Europe) or demonstrate compliance with specific security standards.	All Components	Provider, Deployer	As AIDRec008 relating to running of software and development practices. Includes processes for the secure installation of development software, onboarding of training data and logging of these activities	MAJOR
AIDRec010	Cyber Attacks exposure should be assessed, including when using AI, assessing potential forms of attack to which the platform could be vulnerable to and different types of vulnerabilities and potential entry points for attacks such as those specified in AIDRec011, AIDRec012 and AIDRec013.	All Components	Provider, Deployer	Existing processes should be built upon using the related requirements	MAJOR

ID	Regulatory Requirement	Applicability (component of AIDAVA)	Responsible Party	Acceptance Criteria	Priority
AIDRec011	Data poisoning (i.e. manipulation of training data);	All Components	Provider, Deployer, Data Source	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. To have provided assurance that training data has not been perturbed from capture through curation to upload for training in the form of proof that data supplied matches data that is used for training 2. Logging of all data curation steps (already achieved) and its documentation 	MAJOR
AIDRec012	Model evasion (i.e. classifying the data according to the attacker's will);	All Components	Provider, Deployer, Data Source	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. To have provided assurance that model generation has not been perturbed from capture of source data through curation to analysis for model generation in the form of proof that the model generation processes are documented and implemented as expected 2. Logging of all data curation steps (already achieved) and its documentation 3. Documentation of analysis development for model generation using appropriate unit or system testing 	MAJOR
AIDRec013	Model inversion (i.e. infer the model parameters).	All Components	Provider, Deployer, Data Source	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Ensure that the results of the models cannot be reverse engineered to form insights as to the source data 2. Achieved by limiting access to the analysis process, source data used and output statistical results 3. Document these processes 	MAJOR
AIDRec014	The Platform must be protected by measures to protect the integrity, robustness and its overall security against potential attacks over its lifecycle – which is part of the ongoing DPIA assessments.	All Components	Provider, Deployer	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Results of a periodic DPIA update and review need to be documented in the DPIA processes 2. This needs to be aligned with a documented lifecycle for the system, the data curation and the platform use and development. 	BLOCKING
AIDRec015	The AIDAVA platform, model generation and algorithm training infrastructure should be penetration tested at least annually.	All Components	Provider, Deployer	Production of Penetration Testing Report from all infrastructure partners for storage within the ADIAVA Google Drive	MAJOR

ID	Regulatory Requirement	Applicability (component of AIDAVA)	Responsible Party	Acceptance Criteria	Priority
AIDRec016	The developers must inform users of security measures in place and system updates to maintain the security resilience and operation of the system.	All Components	Provider, Deployer	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> All developer teams must document security measures and updates in release notes for each software update and overall system iteration This will need to be the case for all component developers where updates will need to be communicated for release schedules and presented in after a user logs in. <p>N.B. This may be tabled until deployment in real settings but should be relatively simple</p>	MAJOR
AIDRec017	The developers must identify, assess, and mitigate risks associated with AI deployment.	All Components	Provider, Deployer	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Developers will need to register risks that they identify in the development processes with proposed mitigation measures 	MAJOR
AIDRec018	The developers must implement fail-safe mechanisms that allow the AI tool to be either shut down or be overridden in case of malfunctions or unsafe behaviours.	AI Components	Provider, Deployer	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Evidence of a system function to switch off AI, or a backend function that will deactivate the AI components under these eventualities 	MAJOR
AIDRec019	The developers must ensure that the AI tool does not pose risks to human rights, physical well-being, or societal values.	All Components	Provider, Deployer	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> The developers must present a list of functions and interactions for the tool This can be overlaid with a Fundamental Rights Impact Assessment that WP4 can run 	MAJOR
AIDRec020	The developers must ensure compliance with existing safety regulations such as the MDR and other software and manufacturing standards as relevant	All Components	Provider, Deployer		MINOR

ID	Regulatory Requirement	Applicability (component of AIDAVA)	Responsible Party	Acceptance Criteria	Priority
AIDRec021	AI Providers must offer assurance that these requirements have been met	All Components	Provider	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. This relies on documentation of the processes and functions of the tool as per the preceding requirements 2. Unit or system testing results and validation results need to be provided to verify the documented claims 3. A validation plan on the results and behaviour of the algorithms needs to be provided and updated 4. This validation plan will use the logging and record keeping as specified in AIDRec005 - 007 and AIDRec032 - 037. 	MAJOR
AIDRec022	Any party identified as Providers and Deployers should consider reviewing any DPIA and risk management process as the lifecycle of Algorithm Training and deployment is determined.	All components	Provider, Deployer, Data Source		MINOR
AIDRec023	Providers should map out their development process cycles to overlay the AI Lifecycle as it too is defined.	AI Components	Provider	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. All developers need to specify the lifecycle of their components, the data that is used to train them and the interactions within the platform 2. The tool lifecycle should specify the processes for function development, training, updates, testing and validation, deployment and use, update and evolution and eventual retirement 3. The component lifecycle definition should support the system lifecycle specification 4. Data lifecycle should include data gathering, curation, quality and bias and representation checks, analysis, any update or correction and any removal from the training set 5. The lifecycle specification will be aligned with the validation testing that needs to be documented 	MAJOR

ID	Regulatory Requirement	Applicability (component of AIDAVA)	Responsible Party	Acceptance Criteria	Priority
AIDRec024	For the development pipeline, a review of technical documentation should occur as it is developed to ensure that adequate communication can occur with users.	All components	Provider	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Provision of all technical documentation 2. This includes system specifications and component operation 3. This includes guidance materials and / or instructions manuals 4. This includes details of any design and implementation choices 5. This includes data sources and data items used for training 	BLOCKING
AIDRec025	Providers will work with Deployers and associated interested parties to review the documentation around technical development and articulate in a template that will meet forthcoming requirements as they are developed	All components	Provider, Deployer	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Adherence to the documentation requirements described in AIDRec024 	BLOCKING
AIDRec026	A clearer specification of AI System lifecycle for the tool will be provided to help understand and assess the testing, quality and risk management for the tool as it is deployed and developed	AI Components	Provider	Refer to previous requirements including AIDRec023. Primarily this is documentation related and not something that requires development update	BLOCKING
AIDRec027	This specification will inform any initiative to seek market authorisation under sustainability initiatives	AI Components	Provider		MINOR
AIDRec028	Risk management for the system will overlay with the lifecycle specification outlined above and will mandate a review of the DPIA, DMP and learning from Protocol implementation at sites as the tool is developed and tested.	All components	Provider, Deployer	Refer to previous requirements. Primarily documentation and process related	MAJOR

ID	Regulatory Requirement	Applicability (component of AIDAVA)	Responsible Party	Acceptance Criteria	Priority
AIDRec029	The risk management approach will consider the testing scenarios in Regulatory Sandboxes and Real World Testing.	All components	Provider	Regulatory Sandboxes are not yet defined or deployed (recommend for Market Authorisation).	MINOR
AIDRec030	The Development pipeline will support this approach by ensuring documentation and results are shared for risk and quality management activities.	All components	Provider	Relates to the sharing of evidence as outlined in AIDRec017	MAJOR
AIDRec031	Providers and Deployers will conduct a Fundamental Rights Impact Assessment during Product Assessments, leveraging development pipeline documentation and reports.	All components	Provider, Deployer	Production of a FRIA according to the latest templates available.	MINOR
AIDRec032	Each AI powered or affected component in the architecture will log date, time, process and result of its decision making and operation.	AI Components	Provider	Refer to requirements AIDRec005-007 Logs to include date, time process and results of any decision making or recommendation. This needs to be specific to each component as well as the infrastructure operation. Logs should be harmonised.	MAJOR
AIDRec033	Each AI developed component will present logs in a format that will allow for a full understanding of use of the tool and each of the processes that has been deployed.	All components	Provider, Deployer	Refer to requirements AIDRec005-007. Logs must be human readable via the frontend interface. This needs to be specific to each component as well as the infrastructure operation. Logs should be harmonised.	MAJOR
AIDRec034	A record of data used to train and support decision making and interaction will be kept for each AI component and the Tooling as a whole.	All components	Provider, Deployer	Refer to requirements AIDRec005-007. These records will be used alongside the logs for any validation and user information that may be required	MAJOR

ID	Regulatory Requirement	Applicability (component of AIDAVA)	Responsible Party	Acceptance Criteria	Priority
AIDRec035	The main requirement for the developer pipeline will be to conduct a review of existing QMS activity and add this to the documentation and risk management activities outlined above.	All components	Provider, Deployer	This will require the cataloguing of Quality Management Systems used by Providers and Deployers and will not have impact on the development procedures	MAJOR
AIDRec036	Data sources and AI system Providers must assess and ensure that AI systems are designed and used in an inclusive manner encouraging diverse teams and perspectives to minimise bias.	All components	Providers, Data Sources	In the first stages of Development, an indication of bias will need to be provided most likely to support the validation exercises and to review the documentary evidence. This forms part of the data quality work	MAJOR
AIDRec037	Data sources and AI system Providers must ensure that AI models are trained on datasets that reflect diverse populations to avoid underrepresentation.	All components	Providers, Data Sources	This may not be possible in a smaller study that involves fewer participants from a particular population. This should likely be specified as a limitation of the applicability of the G2 tool, pending further tests as part of a sustainability effort and wider evaluation	MINOR
AIDRec038	Data sources and AI system Providers must ensure that AI systems are usable for people of different ages, abilities, genders, cultural backgrounds, and disabilities.	All components	Providers, Data Sources	This may not be possible in a smaller study that involves fewer participants from a particular population. This should likely be specified as a limitation of the applicability of the Product version of the tool, pending further tests as part of a sustainability effort and wider evaluation	MINOR
AIDRec039	Data sources and AI system Providers must assess source data to identify any potential bias in the data sets.	Training and Model Generation	Providers, Data Sources	As per Data Quality tests in place. Bias needs to be logged but is likely given the small-scale populations that are participating in the programme and studies	MINOR
AIDRec040	Providers should document the results of data quality assessments that identify potential bias.	AI Components	Providers, Data Sources	Provider reporting requirements	MINOR

ID	Regulatory Requirement	Applicability (component of AIDAVA)	Responsible Party	Acceptance Criteria	Priority
AIDRec041	Providers should ensure that the AI does not violate existing legal protections related to race, gender, age, disability, or other protected and vulnerable groups	All Components	Providers	For Market Authorisation	MINOR
AIDRec042	Providers should monitor activity and development to identify bias in the operation of the algorithms	AI Components	Providers, Deployers	Relates to AIDRec032-0037 and the associated requirements. Likely this will relate to existing bias. Part of the monitoring will relate to feedback from Deployers	MINOR
AIDRec043	Providers should establish ethical safeguards through a reporting mechanism for the identification of bias in the AI system and where it occurs.	AI Components	Providers, Deployers	This relates to the reporting of validation tests and their definition however it is harder to implement for a smaller pool of participants. Recommend a testing plan. Review Validation plans. Feedback from Deployers to providers and Providers to Data Sources likely needed (particularly if system bias stems from data bias)	MINOR
AIDRec044	Providers should monitor AI outcomes to ensure that they are balanced and just, ensuring no group is unfairly privileged or harmed.	AI Components	Providers, Deployers	This relates to the reporting of validation tests and their definition however it is harder to implement for a smaller pool of participants. Recommend a testing plan. Review Validation plans. Feedback from Deployers also needed and back to Data Sources if cause of imbalance relates back to data bias	MINOR
AIDRec045	Providers could measure and monitor power utilisation of their processes and servers, and publish a report on this to see if there can be better energy efficiencies discovered in the deployment, operation and therefore development of the AI Components and the system overall.	All components	Providers, Deployers	Could relate back to Deployers	MINOR
AIDRec046	Providers could evaluate greenhouse gas emissions from AI training, deployment, and hardware infrastructure.	All components	Providers, Deployers	Could relate back to Deployers	MINOR

ID	Regulatory Requirement	Applicability (component of AIDAVA)	Responsible Party	Acceptance Criteria	Priority
AIDRec047	Providers and Deployers can utilise responsible use of raw materials for AI hardware, such as data centres and computing devices by optimising and extending the operational life of servers and GPUs through software updates and predictive maintenance, and by encouraging the use of recycled metals (e.g., rare earth elements, aluminium, copper) in the production of AI hardware.	All components	Providers, Deployers		MINOR
AIDRec048	Providers and Deployers can provide a clear assessment on how the implementation of the AI tool will impact employment and/or job displacement.	All components	Providers, Deployers	1. Review of impacts as per study definition and user feedback 2. Likely these are in place but will need to recheck	MAJOR
AIDRec049	Providers and Deployers can conduct surveys to measure public confidence in AI decision-making in healthcare or social services.	All components	Providers, Deployers	Learning from existing participant feedback can help to frame this.	MINOR

4 Conclusions

Re-visiting the comprehensive list of requirements and acceptance criteria, which was elaborated in Phase 1 of Task 1.3 for the AIDAVA prototype, the team assessed 252 of these acceptance criteria as already fulfilled by AIDAVA G1. More specifically, 85% of the 'blocking' acceptance criteria, 52% of the 'major' acceptance criteria, and 38% of the 'minor' acceptance criteria have been fulfilled by the AIDAVA G1 prototype, yet.

Those acceptance criteria (and related requirements) from the comprehensive list compiled in Phase 1 of Task 1.3, which were assessed to not yet be completely fulfilled by the AIDAVA G1 prototype, formed the basis for the compilation of an updated list of requirements and acceptance criteria for the AIDAVA G2 prototype in Phase 2 of Task 1.3. To that list new requirements evolving from practical experience with the AIDAVA G1 prototype and explainability needs were added.

Finally, the consolidated list of business requirements elaborated for the AIDAVA G2 prototype in Phase 2 of Task 1.3 comprises 198 requirements and 355 related acceptance criteria. These 355 acceptance criteria are divided into 289 functional, 17 non-functional and 49 related to training and documentation. Of the 355 acceptance criteria relevant for the AIDAVA prototype, 47% are from patients' perspective, 20% each from curators' and data users' perspective, 7% from administrators' perspective and 5% from 3rd party app developers' perspective. This is in line with AIDAVA seeing patients as the main user group.

34 of the 355 acceptance criteria were prioritised as 'blocking' from users' point of view. Most of these 'blocking' acceptance criteria are related to data curation (10 'blocking'), data publishing (9 'blocking') and user interaction (8 'blocking'). Thus, the main improvements of the AIDAVA prototype will need to be made in these areas and will be the focus of AIDAVA G2 development.

5 Next steps

The business requirements elaborated in Task 1.3 describe from the point of view of the stakeholders (i.e. users, consumers, customers) what functionalities the AIDAVA virtual assistant shall provide, and why these functionalities are needed. This deliverable - and the associated material created during Task 1.3. - is the basis for the elaboration of the formal specifications to be used by the development team; the acceptance criteria are specifically important as they will allow to check if the AIDAVA G2 prototype fulfils the business requirements.

As the next step in the project, GND will review all the requirements and acceptance criteria and integrate these with the technical requirements identified through the AIDAVA G1 prototype development and testing. In the forthcoming meetings with all AIDAVA developer partners, these business requirements and acceptance criteria will be discussed, and a lead developer partner as well as a priority (from developers' point of view) will be assigned to all acceptance criteria, which are seen as 'blocking' or 'major' from users' point of view.

Furthermore, to present possible design solutions for updated user interface and UX features, GND will prepare wireframes. These will be used to validate these solutions with stakeholders and gather their feedback, with a specific focus on the patients through the group of patient consultants. Based on the feedback received, developers will continuously improve and iterate on the solutions.

Next, they will align the system architecture with the solution design and the identified business requirements. This will involve selecting the appropriate tools, technologies, and frameworks required to fulfil the business requirements.

By following this approach, the development will ensure a structured and efficient progression of the project, leading to the delivery of an improved AIDAVA G2 prototype as per the specified requirements.